

Origins of COVID-19
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Coronavirus

This illustration, created at the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), reveals characteristic molecular structure exhibited by coronaviruses. Note the spikes that adorn the outer surface of the virus, which create a bright "corona" surrounding the virion when viewed electron microscopically (See page 19). A novel coronavirus, named Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), was identified as the cause of an outbreak of respiratory illness first detected in Wuhan, China in 2019. The illness caused by this virus has been named coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19).

Date: 2020

Source: National Institute of Health

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<https://phil.cdc.gov/Details.aspx?pid=23311>

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SARS-CoV-2 General Introductory Comments

The world-wide pandemic caused by a novel coronavirus, COVID-19 (SARS-CoV-2), beginning in fall 2019 in Wuhan, China, has cost millions of lives, crippled global economies, and created massive social disarray.

SARS-CoV-2 produces a mild-moderate flu-like illness in the overwhelming majority of victims. However, in a small fraction, a clinical syndrome typified by severe pneumonitis, myocarditis, and widespread DIC (Disseminated Intravascular Coagulation, i.e., extensive de novo clotting in arteries and veins throughout the body) producing extensive organ damage occurs. The immune response in these patients is primarily auto-inflammatory, but a small portion of these patients will develop a catastrophic, auto-immune disorder characterized by the production of autoantibodies.⁽¹⁾

Myriad characteristics of SARS-CoV-2 have been scrutinized; sequencing the virus's genome revealed it to be a member of the beta-coronavirus class,⁽²⁾ to which SARS-CoV-1 and MERS (Middle Eastern Respiratory Syndrome) belong, yet the actual source and origin of SARS-CoV-2 remains wrapped in mystery. This article will examine various clues pointing to its genesis, as that knowledge will potentially help avoid future pandemics.

In the weeks following initial reports of a mysterious respiratory infection in Wuhan, millions of people were allowed to move freely across China to celebrate the Great Lunar New Year before

the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) sealed national borders, placing the entire country under quarantine on January 23, 2020. However, it's estimated the CCP permitted five million travelers to fly out of Wuhan by that date.⁽³⁾ The top ten international destinations for travel were Japan, Thailand, Hong Kong, South Korea, Taiwan, Malaysia, Vietnam, the United States, Singapore, and Australia.⁽³⁾

The CCP and the international scientific community initially announced the virus was natural in origin, jumping from bats, via another animal host, to humans, spreading from a contaminated animal sold at the Wuhan/Huanan Wet Market (WWM), where both live and dead animals are purchased for food and folk medicinals.⁽⁴⁾ However, the CCP has never produced evidence to support a natural emergence explanation.

In stark contrast, both SARS-CoV-1 and MERS viruses left copious traces of their origin in the environment. The intermediate host for SARS-CoV-1 (civets) was identified within four months of the outbreak, and the host of MERS (camels) in nine months. Since the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic started, Chinese researchers have neither determined the original source bat population, or the intermediate animal species to which SARS-CoV-2 purportedly jumped, nor serological evidence that any Chinese residents, including the people of Wuhan, had ever been exposed to SARS-CoV-2 before the fall of 2019.⁽⁴⁾⁽⁵⁾⁽⁶⁾

A serendipitous inventory of the animals (47, 381 individuals from thirty-eight species which included thirty-one protected species) sold at all seventeen wet market shops at the WWM, published in *Nature*⁽⁷⁾, was performed between May 2017 and November 2019. No pangolins (a scaly anteater and a primary suspect for an intermediate host) or bats were traded.

The two closest relatives of SARS-CoV-2 were collected from bats living in caves located in Yunnan, 1500 kilometers from Wuhan. If the virus had first infected inhabitants in Yunnan, it would have confirmed a natural spillover from animals into humans. That did not happen. ⁽⁴⁾

On May 2020, the director of the Wuhan Institute of Virology (WIV), Wang Yanyi declared SARS-CoV-2 “was significantly different from any live pathogen studied at the institute, and that there was no chance it leaked from their laboratories.” ⁽⁷⁾

During the same interview, Wang stated she no longer had samples of a coronavirus (RaTG13) discovered in a Yunnan Province cave bat back in 2013, which the WIV scientists determined to be a 96.2% genetic match to SARS-CoV-2.

In addition, Gao Fu, director of the Chinese CDC, declared in official state media that no animals sold at the WWM had been linked to the virus’s spread to humans. ⁽⁷⁾

A laboratory accident would resemble a natural outbreak if the first exposures only affected a few individuals, compounded by initial, asymptomatic illness. A U.S. Department of State Fact Sheet, published in January 2021, ⁽⁸⁾ affirmed several WIV researchers fell ill in autumn 2019, before the first identified cases of SARS-CoV-2. The report also described earlier cases of accidental lab infections occurring in China, including a 2004 SARS-CoV-1 outbreak in Beijing infecting nine and killing one, as evidence for lab leak problems in the People’s Republic of China (PRC).

The State Department documented the CCP’s activities preventing independent journalists, investigators, or global health authorities to interview any scientists at the WIV, as well as those who fell ill during autumn 2019.

The People's Republic of China Bioweapons Programs

For years, the U.S. has publicly complained about the CCP's past biological weapons work, despite its obligations under the Biological Weapons Convention, and has determined the WIV engaged in classified, secret projects with the Chinese military.⁽⁸⁾⁽⁹⁾

On May 7, 2021, the news site, *The Australian*, reported the existence of a 2015 publication by the Chinese military that openly, and specifically discussed the potential bioweaponization of SARS coronaviruses.⁽¹⁰⁾

The Australian story, republished in *The Epoch Times* on June 2, 2021, recommended STEM (Science Technology Engineering Mathematics) cooperation with China be terminated as the scientific-military considerations outlined in the Chinese military paper represented the epitome of reckless irresponsibility.⁽¹⁰⁾

Contained within that position paper were predictions by Chinese military scientists and senior public health officials that should World War III materialize, it would be decided by employing newly developed biological weapons, not through the use of conventional arms or nuclear weapons.⁽¹⁰⁾

The Epoch Times article stated the military position paper was consistent with prior evidence of offensive Chinese biowarfare research using advanced technologies such as gene-editing and viral gain of function (GoF). The article goes on to say Chinese military researchers have demonstrated particular interest in bioweapon "genetic targeting."⁽¹⁰⁾

Such specific ethnic technology would employ biological weapons targeting restricted, specific human ethnic groups. CRISPR (Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats) technology could be used to facilitate such restricted genetic targeting.⁽¹¹⁾ This technology permits gene editing using CRISPER-Cas, which can act like “scissors” to permit precision editing of a genome.⁽¹²⁾

It is also true that academics and senior officers in the Chinese People’s Liberation Army (PLA) have openly discussed the importance of examining the military potential as well as offensive applications for biotech.⁽¹²⁾⁽¹³⁾

Examples include Senior Colonel Guo Jiwei of the PLA’s Third Military Medical University who co-authored the book, *War for Biological Dominance*, examining the use of biotech in the development of bioweaponry for future warfare.⁽¹⁴⁾ In Chinese, this concept is embodied by the word *zhishengquan* (制生权), which could be translated to mean “biological dominance” or “superiority.”⁽¹⁵⁾

Another vocal proponent for the militarization of biotech has been Major General He Fuchu, a former president of the Academy of Military Medical Sciences who now serves as vice president of the Academy of Military Sciences. He has predicted: “Modern biotechnology and its integration with information, nano(technology), and the cognitive, etc. domains will have revolutionary influences upon weapons and equipment, the combat spaces, the forms of warfare, and military theories.”⁽¹⁶⁾⁽¹⁷⁾

These statements are echoed by General Zhang Shibo, a past president of the PLA’s National Defense University, who in his book, *New Highland of War*, believes current biotech advances

could allow for the creation of new, synthetic pathogens that would be “more toxic, more contagious, and more resistant.”⁽¹²⁾⁽¹⁸⁾

The French government, under the auspices of the Office of the President and France’s Prime Minister, authorized scientific cooperation with the People’s Republic of China (PRC) in 2004 to develop a BSL-4 laboratory (highest level of biological isolation/protection used to study highly infectious agents, such as Ebola, where technicians must wear containment suits with a personal oxygen supply) at the Wuhan Institute of Virology (WIV).⁽¹⁹⁾⁽²⁰⁾

This was done through an agreement between France and the PRC in the aftermath of the 2003 SARS-CoV-1 pandemic. The project was vigorously opposed by French intelligence and defense ministries. The French military had long suspected the PRC of having an active biological warfare program. Therefore, a potential dual-use BSL-4 could be used to develop bioweapons.

With those concerns in mind, the French government negotiated a strict understanding requiring French scientists to be present at the WIV and any contemplated research be conducted by joint French-CCP scientific teams.⁽²⁰⁾

An unusual request by the CCP for dozens of French-made biological containment suits for use at the WIV was denied in 2016, as they were considered an exportation of technologically sensitive equipment.⁽¹⁹⁾ French intelligence blocked the sale and saw it as evidence the CCP was engaging in bioweapon development.⁽¹⁹⁾

Following that denial, in retaliation, French researchers were expelled from the WIV in 2017, with cessation of all scientific cooperation, which caused French officials to warn the U.S. State Department of their grave concerns over the true motivations of the CCP towards the WIV.⁽²¹⁾

In June 2020, the U.S. Department of State (DoS) expressed concerns that China was violating the Biological and Toxin Weapons Convention (BTWC) of 1984 through research employing dual-use technologies. The DoS made similar claims in 2005, 2010, 2012 and 2014. ⁽⁹⁾

The Epoch Times story quotes the original 2015 Chinese military study reported in *The Australian* as stating SARS coronaviruses provide the basis for a “new era of genetic weapons” that can be “artificially manipulated into an emerging human disease virus, then weaponized and unleashed in a way never seen before.” ⁽¹⁰⁾

The report claimed that “following developments in other scientific fields, there have been major advances in the delivery of biological agents. For example, the new-found ability to freeze-dry micro-organisms has made it possible to store biological agents and aerosolize them during attacks.” Tularemia is such a potential bioweapon, where a would-be bioterrorist could grow the bacteria in a lab, then freeze-dry the cultures of *Francisella tularensis*, followed by dispersing the germ as a powdered aerosol to be inhaled by unsuspecting victims. The article discussed how a sudden flood of stricken patients heading to hospitals during a biological weapon attack could “cause the enemy’s medical system to collapse.” ⁽¹⁰⁾

The position paper went on to examine the optimal circumstances for the release of a biological weapon: “Bioweapon attacks are best conducted during dawn, dusk, night, or cloudy weather because intense sunlight can damage the pathogens. Biological agents should be released during dry weather. Rain or snow can cause the aerosol particles to precipitate. A stable wind direction is desirable so that the aerosol can float into the target area.” ⁽¹⁰⁾

The Epoch Times article goes on to argue that due to evidence of China's "criminal" behavior related to informational restrictions regarding COVID-19, its well-documented genocide against the Uyghurs, an extremely aggressive military stance toward the United States and allies, a national strategy of civil-military fusion, ⁽¹¹⁾ dangerous, advanced technologies of gene-targeting, and documented thefts of foreign technologies, the United States and allies should act in concert to restrict or totally suspend all STEM cooperation with China.⁽¹⁰⁾

The Wuhan Institute of Virology

Wuhan Institute of Virology, a research institute by the Chinese Academy of Sciences in Jiangxia District, south of the Wuhan city, Hubei province, China. Photographer: Ureem2805
<https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?title=User:Ureem2805&action=edit&redlink=1>
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/legalcode>

The Wuhan Institute of Virology (WIV) was originally founded as the Wuhan Microbiology Laboratory by two Chinese scientists, Gao Shangyin and Chen Huagui in 1956. ⁽²²⁾ It was established under the auspices of the Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS). Over a twenty-year period, it underwent several name changes and mergers, finally becoming the Wuhan Institute of Virology in 1978. ⁽²²⁾

The WIV performed work on insect viruses, animal viruses, virus classification preservation, research on microbes important in the environment, fermentation, and microbial sensors during the 1980s and 1990s.

Wuhan Institute of Virology http://english.whiov.cas.cn/About_Us2016/Brief_Introduction2016/

In 1998, CAS initiated a multi-pronged project at the WIV specializing in viral and microbial practical application research and biological high-tech innovation. ⁽²²⁾

Following the 2003 SARS-CoV-1 outbreak in China, the WIV, through efforts by the CCP and CAS, was technologically improved further, and its mission broadened, to include a series of medical virus-related research groups focusing on HIV, influenza virus, hepatitis virus, oncological viruses, zoonotic viruses, and investigations examining viral replication and antiviral therapeutics. ⁽²²⁾

As described in an earlier section, ^{(20) (21)} an agreement was signed and implemented by the French and Chinese governments in 2004, enhancing the WIV's ability to study high-level pathogens with the construction of a BSL-4 biohazard laboratory. The BSL-4 was completed in January of 2015. ⁽²²⁾

However, as stated previously, following the denial of a CCP request for high-tech French-manufactured containment suits in 2016 (blocked by French Intelligence), the CCP expelled all French scientists and completely terminated scientific cooperation with France in 2017. ^{(20) (21)}

There is significant circumstantial evidence pointing to the WIV as the source of SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19) with the Huanan Wet Market acting as a “super-spreader” site.

The WIV, the Chinese CDC buildings (where BSL-2 level research on coronaviruses is also performed) and the Huanan wet market (source of over 40% of early cases of COVID-19) are all situated as train stops along the Wuhan Metro Public Railway #2. ⁽⁶⁾

The first four Wuhan hospitals to report clinical cases of COVID-19 all straddle the #2 railway, which on a city map of the system runs north to south, carrying one million passengers daily. ⁽⁶⁾

MAP OF WUHAN METRO SYSTEM 2022

<https://www.travelchinaguide.com/cityguides/hubei/wuhan/subway-map.htm>

The earliest cases were reported involving four individuals interned at the General Hospital of Central Theater Command of the People's Liberation Army (PLA) of China in Wuhan. These patients had the SARS-CoV-2 genetic types, Clade A and Clade B, the viral lineages which have been the genetic viral variants detected in every patient infected worldwide. ⁽²⁴⁾

The WIV is located less than a mile away from that PLA hospital and is the nearest medical facility to the WIV. In addition, both the WIV and the PLA facility are serviced by Line #2 of the Wuhan Metro railway. ^{(6) (24)}

To further facilitate the spread of SARS-CoV-2 throughout the city of Wuhan, Line #2 connects with eight other routes, and services the high-speed Hankou Railway Station, enabling facile spread throughout mainland China, as well as the Wuhan (Tianhe) International Airport, enabling quick dissemination of the virus to Europe, the United States, and the rest of Asia. This is suggested by the dramatically similar genetic strains of SARS-CoV-2 seen in the index patients at the PLA hospital and the international isolates. ^{(6) (24)}

In a publication by Quay and Lee, the authors present the possibility that COVID-19 was already circulating in California (San Francisco) in the first week of 2020, via direct international flights from the Wuhan airport serviced by the Wuhan Metro Line #2. ⁽²⁵⁾

A further set of facts pointing to the WIV as the source of the pandemic and not the Huanan Wet Market is the following excerpt from a July 2020 WHO study ⁽²⁶⁾ which stated:

“The Huanan wholesale market is a large market (653 stalls and more than 1180 employees) mainly supplying seafood products but also fresh fruits and vegetables, meat, and live animals. In late December 2019, ten stall operators were trading live wild animals including chipmunks,

foxes, racoons, wild boar, giant salamanders, hedgehogs, sika deer, and many others. Farmed, wild and domestic animals were also sold at the market including snakes, frogs, quails, bamboo rats, rabbits, crocodiles, and badgers. The market was closed on 1 January 2020, and several investigations followed, including environmental sampling, as well as sampling of frozen animal carcasses at the market. Of the 336 samples collected from animals, none were PCR-positive for SARS-CoV-2, whereas sixty-nine out of 842 environmental samples were positive by PCR for SARS-CoV-2. Sixty-one of those (88%) were from the western wing of the market. Of these, twenty-two samples were from eight different drains and sewage, and three viruses were isolated, sequenced and shared on GISAID. These were virtually identical to the patient samples collected at the same time (>99.9 % homology).”

In comparison, the ninety-one civets and fifteen racoon dogs tested (January 2004) for SARS-CoV-1 from wet markets located in Guangdong Province, China, as sources for the virus were 100% positive, with all 106 animals harboring the pathogen. ⁽²⁷⁾

As previously mentioned, the Wuhan Centers for Disease Prevention and Control (WCDC) is a mere three hundred yards from the Huanan Wet Market. It also studied disease-ridden animals in its research laboratories, which included 605 bats. ⁽⁵⁷⁾

Scientists have espoused the theory that SARS-CoV-2 could have leaked from either the WIV or WCDC and then been spread to the nearby wet market.

A paper published in the Beijing-sponsored South China University of Technology (2020) described how bats housed at the WCDC attacked a researcher and that “the blood of the bat was on his skin.” ⁽⁵⁷⁾

The researcher self-quarantined himself for two weeks following the incident, according to the report. The same individual also quarantined following an incident where a bat urinated on him.

In addition, that same investigator reported discovering a live bat tick on his skin which is known to pass infections through a host animal's blood. ⁽⁵⁷⁾

Further compounding the possibility of a leakage of SARS-CoV-2 from the WCDC is that the first group of physicians infected during the initial weeks of the pandemic were at the Wuhan Union Hospital, adjacent to the WCDC. ⁽⁵⁷⁾

Finally, the testimony of thirty-one residents and twenty-eight visitors to the Huanan Wet Market confirm the local populace does not eat bats as part of their diet. ⁽⁵⁷⁾

Therefore, the first reported outbreaks of COVID-19 among humans appeared in a city which is home to a virology laboratories that actively perform extensive, highly specialized research on coronaviruses situated on a public transit line that physically connected all of the hospitals and transportation facilities initially involved in the worldwide spread of the virus and is almost two thousand kilometers from the nearest cave serving as habitat to bats infected with potentially genetically comparable viral pathogens.

The United Nations World Health Organization (WHO) reported on April 23, 2020, that “all the published genetic sequences of SARS-CoV-2 isolated from human cases are very similar. This suggests that the start of the outbreak resulted from a single point introduction in the human population around the time that the virus was first reported in humans in Wuhan, China in December 2019.” ⁽²³⁾

Finally, if the search for a zoonotic (animal) source for COVID-19 is entertained, the most closely related family of bat coronaviruses (Beta coronaviruses) to SARS-CoV-2 are in Yunnan Province in Southwestern China, 1900 km away from Wuhan. ⁽⁶⁾

The flight range of bats is estimated around 50 km. For a bat-derived COVID-19 precursor virus to make its way from Yunnan to Wuhan province directly, without first infecting many victims along the way, is highly unlikely as no reports of any SARS-CoV-2 infections in the intervening provinces were made prior to the Wuhan outbreak.

Possible Precursor to SARS-CoV-2

In 2015, the WIV top virologist, Shi Zheng-li, with American virologist, Ralph Baric (Baric is credited with developing a general method for engineering bat coronaviruses to attack other species and admits having taught this technique to Shi), ⁽⁴⁾ published a paper (lead author VD Menachery) ⁽²⁸⁾ describing research creating a chimeric virus by combining the spike protein of a bat coronavirus with a mouse-adapted SARS-CoV-1 backbone.

The virus showed robust replication in respiratory cells binding to human angiotensin-converting enzyme II (ACE2), achieving in vitro viral titers equal to epidemic SARS-CoV-1. SARS-based immune therapeutics had poor efficacy against the novel spike protein.

The authors thought this dramatic augmentation in pathogenicity positioned this type of research at a crucial crossroads in the execution of so-called “Gain-of-Function” research (GoF). ⁽²⁸⁾

This unusual pathogen could have been a prototype to SARS-CoV-2. What gave this particular virus the capacity to infect humans so readily with such high efficiency (infectivity) was the presence of the **Furin Sequence**, a unique, artificially inserted/added cleavage site on the key molecule permitting cellular entry, the SARS Spike Protein.

The Furin Site

For SARS-CoV-2 to enter a human cell, the virus' primary attachment molecule, the Spike Protein, must first bind to a cellular surface structure called the Angiotensin Converting Enzyme-2 receptor (ACE-2).⁽¹⁾

After attaching itself to the target cell receptor, the still infectious inactive Spike Protein (SP) requires the host cell to “cut” the molecule into its two, active subunit pieces, S1 and S2, by a human, membrane-bound, serine protease – TMPRSS2.⁽²⁹⁾

The TMPRSS2 enzyme cleaves the SP at a very specific location within the structure called the *Furin Cleavage Site (FCS)*, a series of arginine molecules (specific amino acids along the protein chain). Once the TMPRSS2 binds to these arginine residues and “cuts” the inactive SP, the two subunits, S1 and S2, do their “dirty work.”

Coronavirus: Protein Spike Corona

A colorized transmission electron micrograph of the Middle East respiratory syndrome-related Coronavirus (MERS-CoV) that emerged in 2012.

Date: November 19, 2012

Source: National Institute of Health

Public domain [image](#) from National Institutes of Health

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Middle_East_respiratory_syndrome-related_coronavirus.jpg

Half of the “spike” —its S1 subunit—allows firm attachment of the SARS-CoV-2 to the surface of the target cell, securely anchoring the invader to its victim.

The S2 subunit ensures entry by catalyzing fusion between the SARS-CoV-2's fatty membrane with that of the gargantuan target cell. ^{(1) (29)}

With full access to the host's cytoplasm, the SARS-CoV-2's single-stranded RNA genome hijacks the cell's manufacturing abilities by binding to protein-synthesizing ribosomes anchored to the perinuclear, rough endoplasmic reticulum.

Ribosomal translation of the encrypted viral RNA results in the synthesis of a handful of polyproteins, which then self-catalyze and cleave into smaller, functional fragments—the raw materials necessary for replication of the invader's RNA genome, and several key structural and non-structural proteins required for the delicate birthing of new siblings.

Further augmenting infectivity, the SARS-CoV-2 coerces the invaded, zombie-like cell to grow and radially array actin-rich, cytoskeletal branched filopodia (tentacles). ⁽³⁰⁾

Each of the filopods contains multiple M-protein clusters capable of producing more siblings of the SARS-CoV-2.

These sword-like appendages forcibly pierce the membranes of adjacent, innocent host cells, reaching deep into their cytosols.

The protuberances burst, releasing fresh kin which then commandeer the newly violated victim.

The host's immune system offers little to no resistance because of the viral suppression of Interleukin-1 and Interleukin-3, lymphocytic chemokines (intercellular molecular messengers) necessary for the activation of antiviral defenses, ^{(31) (32)} which allows silent virion shedding, and the subsequent infection of new hosts.

But none of this would be possible without the artificial insertion of a group of arginine amino acids, the FCS, into the SP's structure.

FCS have been found in viruses that can infect human cells, such as influenza and HIV. SARS-CoV-2 is a member of the Beta Coronavirus Family. **No naturally occurring virus in this entire group has an FCS as part of the native SP structure.** ⁽⁶⁾ (Author emphasis)

Review of a database containing the complete genomic sequences of 386 coronaviruses revealed the complete absence of an FCS. ⁽³³⁾

In addition, the first paper using Furin Inhibitors (FI) demonstrating the importance and necessity of an FCS for successful coronavirus-cell fusion was published in 2004. ⁽³⁴⁾

The discovery of a twelve-nucleotide long section in SARS-CoV-2 RNA which coded for a SP containing a four amino acid long segment with arginine residues (FCS), essential for human infectivity and transmission, should have prompted worldwide scientific interest in an artificial source for the pathogen.

By 2017, the WIV had openly revealed through the publication of multiple scientific papers, that it had developed the necessary laboratory techniques to collect novel coronaviruses, to modify and improve the virus' receptor binding domain permitting human transmission, to insert furin sites allowing human cell infection, to create both chimera and synthetic viruses, the ability to perform experiments in humanized mice, and to modify a gene called ORF8, thus increasing the lethality of the artificial virus to promote human cell death (apoptosis). ⁽⁶⁾ ⁽³⁵⁾

Therefore, the WIV possessed all the scientific technology necessary to create a virus like SARS-CoV-2. (Author emphasis)

These types of experiments are commonly known as *Gain of Function (GoF)*.

Gain of Function

“GoF involves experimentation that aims or is expected to increase the transmissibility and/or virulence of pathogens.”⁽³⁶⁾ Despite potential benefits, these types of investigations can be engaged for both benevolent or malevolent purposes, which is why in 2014 the Obama Administration ordered a “temporary pause” on federal funding of GoF involving influenza, SARS, and MERS viruses.⁽³⁶⁾

Another way to describe GoF research would be any investigation designed to introduce *de novo* genetic mutations conferring altered functionality to a specified protein or other essential pathogenic cellular molecule.⁽³⁷⁾ A further way to illustrate this is that these artificial mutations can result in a particular protein of interest’s loss of function or augmentation of function (GoF).

Scientists who promote this type of research say such artificial modifications both improve the understanding of disease pathogenesis and spur progress towards medical countermeasures to combat yet to emerge infectious diseases.⁽³⁷⁾

Prior to the emergence of SARS-CoV-2, GoF research had provoked controversy, particularly as it relates to *Dual Use Research of Concern (DURC)*.⁽³⁷⁾

DURC, a subset of microbiology investigations can, as defined by the US government, “be reasonably anticipated to provide knowledge, information, products, or technologies that could be directly misapplied to pose a significant threat with broad potential consequences to public health and safety, agricultural crops and other plants, animals, the environment, materiel, or national security.”⁽³⁸⁾

Some potential consequences of DURC include the manipulation of pathogens for use as biological weapons with modifications permitting the newly created organisms to evade countermeasures.⁽³⁹⁾

These possibilities have raised concerns among funders for biological research, such as the National Institutes of Health (NIH), that such research “could be used for intentionally harmful purposes or result in an accidental release of pathogens from the laboratory into the general population.”⁽³⁷⁾

Several of the most successful vaccines developed, such as the live-attenuated types, have resulted from GoF research. Examples include polio and smallpox, whose live attenuated vaccines produce immunity against multiple versions of the pathogens without generating disease in the recipient.

For instance, the currently used measles vaccine is a live-attenuated version that was created in the laboratory through passage of the virus through multiple viral cultures until mutations arose that changed the level of pathogenicity, a common technique employed in GoF research.⁽⁴⁰⁾

Other proponents of GoF research point to an improved understanding of the epidemiology of emerging pathogens, thus improving methods for conducting surveillance of future outbreaks. Such an example would be research on influenza regarding the relative transmissibility of hemagglutinin mutations which alter and modify the virus's infectivity. ⁽⁴¹⁾

However, concerns remain over the malevolent use of DURC in the production of biological weapons of mass destruction.

Research conducted which has driven such concerns include the genetic engineering of a superstrain of the mousepox virus in 2001, ⁽⁴²⁾ the laboratory synthesis (through synthetic genomics) of a "live" polio virus from chemical components in 2002, ⁽⁴³⁾ and the reconstruction (through synthetic genomics) of the deadly "Spanish Flu of 1918" in 2005. ⁽⁴⁴⁾

Even though the aims of these various experiments were legitimate, critics argue that they should not have been conducted and/or published, as these papers provided "full detail recipes" for potentially dangerous biological weapons to be used by would-be bioterrorists. Those who acknowledged such potential dangers argued the benefits of such publications outweigh the risks involved. ⁽³⁶⁾

However, the risks remain. Concerns surround various issues, such as biocontainment. Critics of DURC and GoF argue that these kinds of experiments should be exclusively conducted in BSL-4 labs, thus decreasing the possibility of accidental release and creation of a potentially devastating pandemic. ⁽⁴⁵⁾ As DURC/GoF research interest and experimentation grows, similar work might

be conducted in sub-optimal conditions in countries/institutions with a weaker technological infrastructure or research oversight.⁽⁴⁶⁾

Another concern is the relatively small number of individuals and institutions involved in the execution and overseeing of DURC/GoF research. Critics argue for the necessity of broader community engagement and consultation for more transparent decision and policy making.⁽⁴⁷⁾

(48) (49)

Due to the potential dangers and benefits of DURC/GoF research affecting the public at large, the argument has been made that more public debate and decision-making is needed, as it is ethically troublesome for a small group of scientists to be making decisions and taking actions that could impose serious risks on others without their consent or adequate input, particularly as the potential ramifications of DURC/GoF could be global in nature.⁽⁵⁰⁾

A prominent researcher/ethicist, David Relman puts it this way:⁽⁴⁷⁾

“Woefully insufficient input has been obtained from a wide variety of scientists and from many other stakeholders among the general public. It is unethical to place so many members of the public at risk and then consult only scientists—or, even worse, just a small subset of scientists—and exclude others from the decision-making and oversight process... In many cases, conversations have only involved infectious-disease researchers and conflicts of interests among participants have not been adequately acknowledged or addressed... It is our responsibility as scientists to explain the rationale behind our work, including its benefits and risks, to the general public in terms that are accessible to those with an average level of education, rather than to be

dismissive. This is especially important when the work has important consequences for the whole of society.”

In 2012, a paper submitted by Herfst S, et al., ⁽⁵¹⁾ called “Airborne Transmission of Influenza A/H5N1 Virus Between Ferrets” published in *Science*, described how they had genetically modified the A/H5N1 virus through site-directed mutagenesis and serial passage in ferrets, creating a viral strain capable of airborne transmission in ferrets. The possible accidental or malicious intentional release of such a virus into the environment prompted the Obama Administration to halt all funding for GoF research related to SARS, influenza, or MERS in 2014, although this decision has been since rescinded. ⁽⁵²⁾

There is widespread agreement among researchers that the biosafety risks posed by DURC/GoF could be minimized by implementation of some of the following measures: ⁽⁵³⁾ ⁽⁵⁴⁾ ⁽⁵⁵⁾

- Use of pathogens with a low-level virulence.
- Pathogens for which natural immunity exists, or which there are pre-existing vaccines.
- Organisms which have been modified so to prevent replication outside of a controlled laboratory environment.
- The development of broad-spectrum vaccines.
- Vaccination of the laboratory personnel thus creating a “ring of immunity.”
- Open-ended, ongoing improvements in biosafety procedures, practice, and infrastructure.

The debate over DURC/GoF will continue, as the unfortunate truth is that many countries, including the United States, are routinely conducting, and funding this type of research, whether

for purely scientific purposes, or for malevolent intent. The reality is that there will be future pandemics as opening this biological “Pandora’s Box” remains too tempting to resist. ⁽⁵⁶⁾

The Multi-Faceted Cover Up Surrounding COVID-19

Examination of “how” vital scientific and epidemiological information was suppressed and distorted during a worldwide pandemic following the appearance of SARS-CoV-2 in Wuhan, China, will be discussed in the sections to follow.

Initial Appearance and Timeline of SARS-CoV-2

The official outbreak started in late December 2019 with news reports describing the sudden appearance of an unexplained pneumonia cluster in the Chinese city of Wuhan that did not resemble any previously known pulmonary infection in humans, associated with resistance to available antivirals and antibiotics and a high death rate. ⁽⁵⁸⁾

It was reported that some of the stricken individuals worked at the same seafood market (Huanan Wet Market), which was said to sell birds, pheasants, snakes, and the organs of rabbits and other animals for food.

However, Chinese authorities repeatedly put roadblocks hampering the free flow of information from the very start of the growing medical crisis.

A physician, Dr. Li Wenliang, was among the first to sound the alarm. He had helped treat seven patients suffering from the unknown illness and decided to send out a warning to his medical school classmates via an online chat group on Dec 30, 2019, declaring he and the patients were “Quarantined in the emergency department.”⁽⁵⁹⁾

Following the posting of the warning, officials from the local health authority in the city of Wuhan summoned the physician in the middle of the night, demanding to know why he felt the special need to share this information with colleagues.

Three days later, Dr. Li was forced by the local police to sign a statement admitting that his warning constituted “illegal Behavior.”⁽⁵⁹⁾

After Dr. Li’s warning was shared by several of his medical school classmates, the authorities focused their efforts at controlling the evolving portrayal of the problem. The police crackdown began with an announcement of an investigation of eight individuals for spreading “rumors.”

On the same day, the Wuhan Health Commission, in response to the “rumors,” announced twenty-seven people were sick from a pneumonia of unknown cause. The official statement declared “there was no reason to be alarmed.”⁽⁵⁹⁾

“The disease is preventable and controllable,” the proclamation said.

Following his reprimand, Dr. Li, an ophthalmologist, returned to work, treating a woman on Jan 10, 2020, for glaucoma. She had been infected with SARS-CoV-2, likely by her daughter, and because of the exposure, Dr. Li became ill and succumbed to the disease.

In the weeks to follow, Chinese authorities systematically silenced physicians and other Wuhan residents for raising concerns about the increasing number of new cases. They minimized the dangers to the public, thus preventing individuals from taking any meaningful measures to protect themselves. It was this stonewalling of the dissemination of vital information that led international public health experts to say the Chinese government frustrated one of its best opportunities to prevent the COVID-19 epidemic. ⁽⁵⁹⁾

“This was an issue of inaction,” said Yanzhong Huang, a senior fellow for global health at the Council on Foreign Relations who studies China. “There was no action in Wuhan from the local health department to alert people to the threat.” ⁽⁵⁹⁾

The New York Times reported the first case of what would be eventually known as SARS-CoV-2, or COVID-19, occurred in early December 2019. ⁽⁵⁹⁾

Physicians and nurses staffing the local Wuhan hospitals were baffled by the clusters of patients coming to their E.R.s with symptomatic viral pneumonias unresponsive to standard treatment regimens. However, when they obtained detailed medical histories, it soon became evident that many of the victims had one thing in common: employment at the Huanan Wet Market. ⁽⁵⁹⁾

On Jan 1, 2020, police officers, accompanied by local health officials, shut down the wet market. The public health officials announced the market was to undergo an environmental and hygienic cleanup due to the respiratory cases, donning hazmat suits, spraying disinfectants, and washing out stalls. ⁽⁵⁹⁾

The Wuhan Huanan Wholesale Seafood Market, believed to be the source of the coronavirus sits closed in Wuhan, China, Tuesday, Jan. 21, 2020. (AP Photo/Dake Kang)

<https://www.timesofisrael.com/wuhans-virus-ground-zero-market-hides-in-plain-sight/>

On Dec 31, 2019, the day prior to the market shutdown, national authorities had contacted the World Health Organization's office in Beijing notifying them of an outbreak.

Wuhan political officials used unusual optimism to announce at this time that their "efforts" had stopped the virus at its source as the cluster of ill patients was limited, and the proclaimed "there was no evidence the virus spread between humans." (59)

“Projecting optimism and confidence, if you don’t have the data, is a very dangerous strategy,” said Alexandra Phelan, a faculty research instructor in the Department of Microbiology and Immunology at Georgetown University. ⁽⁵⁹⁾

“It undermines the legitimacy of the government in messaging,” she added. “And public health is dependent on public trust.”

On Jan 10, 2020, the first fatality due to COVID-19 occurred, involving a man identified as “Zeng,” who suffered from chronic liver disease and an undisclosed tumor of the abdomen. He had checked into the Wuhan Puren Hospital complaining of shortness of breath and a very high fever. ⁽⁵⁹⁾

A medical colleague of Dr. Li, Lu Xiaohong, chair of the Department of Gastroenterology at Wuhan City Hospital No. 5 reportedly noted that by Dec 25, 2019, the unknown disease was spreading among medical workers, a full three weeks before health authorities would acknowledge that fact. She apparently warned a school near the wet market but did not go public with her suspicions. ⁽⁵⁹⁾

By Jan 8, 2020, the E.R. at Hospital No. 5 was overflowing with patients suffering from the “unknown” illness, with many of the cases occurring in family clusters, all during the “no human-to-human spread” declarations of the Wuhan health officials. ⁽⁵⁹⁾

During this time, Dr. Shi, the Director of the WIV, and her co-workers successfully isolated the viral strain and determined its genetic sequence using samples obtained from seven of the first index patients, six of which had been vendors at the Huanan Market.

The WIV scientists baptized the new coronavirus by the technical shorthand 2019-nCoV, and announced the virus's genetic sequence on Jan 11, 2020, recording the information in a public database for scientists worldwide to access. ⁽⁵⁹⁾

On Jan 7, 2020, the mayor of Wuhan, Zhou Xianwang, was addressing the city's People's Congress, the CCP-run legislature which serve as a propaganda forum to tout the "wonders of communism," against a backdrop of scarlet national flags, outlining plans to modernize Wuhan's medical industrial parks, but failing to mention anything about the viral outbreak, or the already firm evidence of human-to-human transmission and the mounting illnesses among health care workers. ⁽⁵⁹⁾

"Stressing politics is always No. 1," the governor of Hubei, Wang Xiaodong, told officials on Jan. 17, 2020, citing President Xi's precepts of top-down obedience. "Political issues are at any time the most fundamental major issues." ⁽⁵⁹⁾

During the third week of January 2020, Wuhan celebrated an annual, massive potluck reception for over 40,000 families, clear evidence of the careless approach local leaders took towards outbreak. ⁽⁵⁹⁾

The government's efforts to tamp down the free flow of relevant information even convinced physicians in other cities. Dr. Guan Yi, a prominent professor of infectious disease at the University of Hong Kong, is quoted as saying, "If there are no new cases in the next few days, the outbreak is over." ⁽⁵⁹⁾

Public pronouncements by the WHO regarding the outbreak echoed the propaganda of Chinese officials.

However, on Jan 13, 2020, the first case was reported in Thailand, confirming the spread of the virus outside China's national borders. ⁽⁵⁹⁾

The publicity generated by this first extra-national case finally garnered the attention of authorities in Beijing, prompting the national government to send Zhong Nanshan, a prominent epidemiologist who was instrumental in investigating the SARS-CoV-1 outbreak to Wuhan to investigate the evolving epidemic. ⁽⁵⁹⁾

On Jan 20, 2020, Dr. Zhong announced in a TV interview broadcast on state media, that “there was no doubt the new coronavirus was transmissible between humans,” and that one patient had purportedly infected fourteen medical workers. ⁽⁵⁹⁾

President Xi Jinping, returning from a state visit to Myanmar, finally made his first public pronouncements about the Wuhan outbreak on Jan 7, 2020. The announcement of measures to be taken finally prompted the bureaucracy to act. By that time, three patients had expired. However, the death toll would rise above two hundred in just a matter of a few days. Xi did not officially address the Chinese public regarding the evolving coronavirus outbreak until Jan 20, 2020. ⁽⁶⁰⁾

Wuhan officials banned tourists, and residents who started donning facemasks to protect themselves.

A few days later, the local authorities announced a lockdown of the entire city, an action which had to have been approved by the central national government.

However, despite this chronology of events, there remains a major, unexplained mystery. Why did spending on PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction) equipment and supplies, a key technology

employed in the detection of illnesses such as SARS-CoV-2, soar several months before the first official reporting of COVID-19 cases? ⁽⁶¹⁾

The cybersecurity firm, Internet 2.0, an Australian entity, was tracking the sales of PCR testing machines and kits over several years, observing a nearly 50% increase between 2018 to 2019—the year before the COVID-19 outbreak spread across the world, implying a possibility that COVID-19 was already in circulation in Chinese communities during the summer of 2019, long before public recognition by the CCP. ⁽⁶¹⁾

“Sales of PCR tests, used to detect specific viruses, totaled 19.1 million yuan (AU\$4 million) in 2016, before rising to 29.1 million yuan (AU\$6 million) in 2017, 36.7 million yuan in 2018, and 67.4 million yuan (AU\$14 million) in 2019.” ⁽⁶¹⁾

According to the report, “Procuring for a Pandemic: An Assessment of Hubei Province (China) PCR Procurement Assessments”, ⁽⁶²⁾ their research findings “challenge existing assumptions around when the pandemic began and support further investigation. The study concludes a significant increase in spending in PCR equipment correlated with the spread of COVID-19.”

“We assess with medium confidence the significant increase from 2018 to 2019 in Hubei province (67.4 million yuan of total PCR equipment in 2019) is due to an event like the emergence of COVID-19.” ⁽⁶²⁾

“Finally, we assess with high confidence that the pandemic began much earlier than China informed the WHO about COVID-19.” ⁽⁶²⁾

The Internet 2.0 study was conducted looking at 1,716 procurement contracts spanning from 2007 to 2019.

The investigation revealed a “notable, significant and abnormal” number of PCR equipment procurements in 2019 by Wuhan-based entities like the People’s Liberation Army Airborne Army Hospital, (May 2019), the WIV (November 2019), the Wuhan University of Science and Technology (October 2019) and finally, the Hubei Province Districts Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (May-December 2019). ⁽⁶²⁾

There currently is no official explanation by the PLA nor the CCP for the reasons behind these unusual and inherently suspicious procurements.

China’s COVID-19 Propaganda War

To compound the questions surrounding the emergence of COVID-19 in China, the CCP did and continues to wage a scathing propaganda war in attempts to obfuscate investigations into the origin of the virus. ^{(63) (64)}

Dr. Li Wenliang

<https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-china-51364382>

In early Feb 2020, news spread through social media that Dr. Li Wenliang, the beforementioned Wuhan physician who had issued warnings to local medical personnel and colleagues that there was a strange, new viral outbreak occurring, had not only been threatened by police and accused of spreading false rumors, but had purportedly died of COVID-19. To many, the death of Dr. Li was a concrete example of the terrible consequences incurred by anyone who dared speak the truth, crushed by the CCP's instinct to stifle the exposure of embarrassing information.

The CCP ordered news websites to silence notifications alerting readers of his untimely death, removing Li's name from trending topics pages, and ordering hundreds of fake online commentators to inundate social sites with extraneous chatter, emphasizing for "discretion."⁽⁶⁵⁾

The CCP's censors issued specific instructions directing management of stories and chatter about Dr. Li's passing.

For social media platforms and news websites, the censors ordered:

"... do not use push notifications, do not post commentary, do not stir up speculation. Safely control the fervor in online discussions, do not create hashtags, gradually remove from trending topics, strictly control harmful information."⁽⁶⁵⁾

Instructions to local propaganda agents consisted of:

"We must recognize with clear mind the butterfly effect, broken windows effect and snowball effect triggered by this event, and the unprecedented challenge that it has posed to our online

opinion management and control work. All Cyberspace Administration bureaus must pay heightened attention to online opinion, and resolutely control anything that seriously damages party and government credibility and attacks the political system ...”⁽⁶⁵⁾

These orders, and thousands of secret Chinese government directives and other pertinent documents had been reviewed by *The New York Times* and *ProPublica* investigative reporters. They show the existence of elaborate systems employed by the CCP to mold and influence online information about the pandemic.⁽⁶⁵⁾

Although it is well-known the CCP makes no secret of its rigid internet controls, these documents reviewed by *The New York Times* and *ProPublica* delineate the depth of the behind-the-scenes efforts exercised by Chinese central authorities in maintaining a steel-grip on the dissemination of information.

In early January 2020, the documents show the CCP’s efforts to clamp down on the free dissemination of information began before SARS-CoV-2 had even been definitively identified as the culprit behind the outbreak of mysterious lower respiratory infections in Wuhan.⁽⁶⁵⁾

Per *The New York Times* report, more than 3,200 directives and 1,800 memos and files from the Chinese internet regulator, the Cyberspace Administration of China, based in the eastern city of Hangzhou, as well as internal files from the Chinese company, Urun Big Data Services, a manufacturer of software employed by local governments to monitor internet traffic and manage armies of “bots,” were supplied to the newspaper by a hacker group called C.C.P. Unmasked.

Per *The New York Times* piece, “China has a politically weaponized system of censorship; it is refined, organized, coordinated, and supported by the state’s resources,” said Xiao Qiang, a research scientist at the School of Information at the University of California, Berkeley, and the founder of the *China Digital Times*. “It’s not just for deleting something. They also have a powerful apparatus to construct a narrative and aim it at any target with huge scale. This is a huge thing,” he added. “No other country has that.”⁽⁶⁵⁾

President Xi Jinping of the People’s Republic of China
https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Xi_Jinping_March_2017.jpg

Xi Jinping, General Secretary of the CCP Central Committee, Chairman of the Central Military Commission, and President of the PRC, ordered the creation of the Cyberspace Administration in 2014 to centralize the control of internet censorship and propaganda. Cyberspace reports directly to the CCP Central Committee.

“News outlets were told not to play up reports on donations and purchases of medical supplies from abroad. The concern, according to agency directives, was that such reports could cause a backlash overseas and disrupt China’s procurement efforts, which were pulling in vast amounts of personal protective equipment as the virus spread abroad.”⁽⁶⁵⁾

To control the evolving crisis, President Xi reshuffled leadership in Hubei province, which contains Wuhan, installing protégés willing to strictly follow the CCP propaganda goals.⁽⁶⁶⁾

In addition to local efforts, the CCP lobbied the WHO to decline declaring the Wuhan epidemic a global health emergency, thereby discouraging efforts by other countries to develop coherent, cooperative strategies to contain and stop the spread of SARS-CoV-2.⁽⁶⁷⁾

The WHO instead declared Chinese health officials were sufficiently capable and equipped to combat the Wuhan outbreak. Therefore the agency did not need the additional authoritative powers that would arise from such a declaration. These powers, under the acronym, PHEIC (Public Health Emergency of International Concern) grant the WHO’s Director-General the ability to issue binding recommendations for how countries should proceed to contain an epidemic.

The Chair of the WHO Emergency Committee, Didier Houssin, stated members were divided about the need to declare a PHEIC, and that the group deemed it “too early” for the Director-General Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus to authorize such a proclamation. ⁽⁶⁷⁾ Houssin stated some members felt that as there were so few cases outside of China, and as Chinese health authorities had instituted specific actions to contain the virus, the outbreak did not merit a global health emergency declaration. ⁽⁶⁷⁾

Throughout January 2020, the WHO instead heaped praise upon China for taking a speedy response to SARS-CoV-2. It made repeated statements thanking the CCP for sharing the genetic mapping of the virus “immediately” and declared the work and commitment of the CCP as “transparent, very impressive, and beyond words.” ⁽⁶⁸⁾

However, as reported by *The Associated Press/NBC News*, ⁽⁶⁸⁾ instead the real story was one of significant delay tactics by the CCP leading to enormous frustration among WHO officials due to the inability of obtaining timely information needed to properly combat the viral outbreak.

Despite the public praise, the CCP in fact had blocked the release of the genome (genetic makeup) of SARS-CoV-2 for more than a week after three separate government laboratories had fully sequenced the virus. The iron fisted grip of information by the CCP was to blame. ⁽⁶⁸⁾

The genome was finally released by the CCP only after another lab published it on a virologist’s website on Jan 11, 2020. To make matters worse, the CCP withheld vital patient and case information for another two weeks. ⁽⁶⁸⁾

This purposeful delay prevented the recognition of the spread of SARS-CoV-2 to other countries, as well as the concurrent development of testing protocols and devices, antiviral drugs, and possible vaccines. The paucity of clinical patient data also made it impossible to gauge the pathogen's speed of spread.

The time delay between the initial sequencing by a Chinese government lab on Jan 2, 2020, and the day the WHO finally declared a global health emergency on Jan 30, 2020, allowed the viral outbreak expansion to increase 200-fold, per a retrospective infection data analysis by the Chinese CDC. ⁽⁶⁸⁾

In addition, despite the Chinese CDC internally declaring the Wuhan outbreak a “level-one emergency,” the highest level possible, the CCP still stated publicly that the chance of human-to-human transmission was very low. ⁽⁶⁸⁾

According to the *AP/NBC News* story, the WHO hotly debated the possibility of limited human-to-human transmission. However, publicly the WHO backtracked, tweeting that “preliminary investigations conducted by the Chinese authorities have found no clear evidence of human-to-human transmission”—a statement that later became fodder for critics. ⁽⁶⁸⁾

Despite case counts exploding in Wuhan, the CCP continued to drag its feet, choking the release of important clinical and scientific information. It was learned that Beijing city authorities considered locking down the capital in light of the growing Wuhan crisis, according to a medical expert with direct knowledge of the deliberations. ⁽⁶⁸⁾

On Jan 28, 2020, Director-General Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus took several top WHO experts to Beijing to meet with Xi Jinping and other senior CCP officials to discuss the Wuhan outbreak.

After the meeting, Tedros announced China had agreed to welcome an international team of scientific and infectious disease experts. The Director-General heaped praise on Xi and the CCP despite the repeated stonewalling by Chinese authorities. ⁽⁶⁸⁾

During the WHO activities, and the information blackout by the CCP, the Chinese government continued a propaganda blitz, publishing stories in the *Chinese Global Times* (GT), an English-language daily tabloid newspaper under the control of the Chinese Communist Party's flagship newspaper, *The People's Daily*. The *GT* traditionally publishes articles presenting a Chinese ultra-nationalistic point of view of local and world events.

The *GT* published multiple articles blaming other countries for the Wuhan outbreak.

It initially published an article claiming SARS-CoV-2 came from Italy, ⁽⁶⁹⁾ followed by the statement:

“Not just in Italy, other scientific studies also suggest the novel coronavirus appeared in the US in mid-December 2019 and in France in late December, before or around the time the virus was officially identified in China.”

The *GT* even made claims that frozen food imported from other countries carried the virus into Wuhan. ⁽⁷⁰⁾

The New York Times reported the CCP claimed SARS-CoV-2 was brought to Wuhan by members of the U.S. Army who visited the city in October 2019. ⁽⁷¹⁾

The *NYT* article stated the Chinese Ministry of Foreign Affairs had made an official announcement on Twitter pushing the claim, despite not producing any evidence to support it. Their spokesman, Zhao Lijian, accused the Americans of “not coming clean about what they knew about the disease.”

The Pentagon had sent seventeen teams comprising 280 athletes and other staff members to the Military World Games held in Wuhan during the month of October 2019, long before there had been any official mention of a viral outbreak in China.

Indeed, there was evidence of cases not related to the Huanan Wet Market occurring earlier than the official CCP December 2019-January 2020 timeline. One patient was reported in *The Lancet* ⁽⁷²⁾ whose symptoms started on December 1, 2019, and had no association with the wet market.

The South China Morning Post reported nine cases occurring in November 2019, listing their age and sex, none of which could be labelled as “patient zero.” ⁽⁷³⁾

In an interview with a Professor Yu Chuanhua of the Wuhan University published in the *Health Times*, he described two cases from mid-November and one suspected case from September 29, 2019, that were entirely consistent with infection by SARS-CoV-2. ⁽⁷⁴⁾

Following Professor Yu's interview, the Chinese CDC disseminated an order absolutely forbidding the distribution and release of any information about the SARS-CoV-2 epidemic sans official approval. ⁽⁷⁵⁾ As a result, Yu re-contacted the *Health Times* to say that the earlier cases could not be confirmed to be COVID-19. ⁽⁷⁴⁾

This proclamation by the China CDC was broadened and strengthened by orders issued by the PRC's State Council, requiring ALL publications related to COVID-19 be pre-approved by the government entity before release to the public. ⁽⁷⁶⁾

In another coordinated attempt to snuff out evidence of the SARS-CoV-2 epidemic starting earlier than the official timeline narrative, a joint WHO-China position paper dismissed all reported cases of COVID-19 prior to December 8, 2019, and pushed the theory that SARS-CoV-2 definitely came from the Huanan Wet Market, despite a lack of firm scientific data supporting the contention. ⁽⁷⁷⁾

Further evidence of documented obfuscation by the CCP in their propaganda war and information suppression was a report published in the *South China Morning Post* describing an official government proclamation ordering all unauthorized Chinese labs to destroy their

coronavirus samples collected during the early part of the epidemic, reportedly for “laboratory biological safety.”⁽⁷⁹⁾

The Wuhan viral genetic sequences that have been made available have confounded attempts at phylogenetic analyses designed to discover the earliest “pro-genitor” of the SARS-CoV-2 virus, which is the sequence from which the entirety of “known” genetic sequences have descended from.⁽⁷⁹⁾

These early SARS-CoV-2 sequences derived from the Huanan Seafood market are very different from sequences obtained from specimens collected at later dates outside of Wuhan. This results in a direct conflict between two primary scientific principles employed in the attempt to infer an outbreak’s progenitor, specifically, it’s genetic sequence should be among the earliest sequences, and that it should be most closely related to deeper ancestors.⁽⁸⁰⁾

Additional Chinese propaganda expressed the CCP’s displeasure with President Trump’s January 31, 2020, decision to ban flights from China following the detection of the first confirmed infection with COVID-19 in the U.S.A. An article in the *GT* claimed the President’s order was an “overreaction which would greatly hurt global tourism and hinder people-to-people exchanges” per Ni Feng, deputy director of the Institute of American Studies of the Chinese Academy of Social Sciences.⁽⁸¹⁾

The American decision was coupled in part to the announcement by the WHO calling the novel coronavirus epidemic in Wuhan, China, a “Public Health Emergency of International Concern”

(PHEIC). The *GT* article stressed the decision by the WHO did not require countries to set travel or trade restrictions. The Chinese official predicted other Western countries might replicate the U.S.' decision.

The American declaration was also criticized by the China CDC Chief Epidemiologist, Zeng Guang, suggesting the "U.S.' declaration was a demonstration of its unilateralism," which Zeng did not find unsurprising.

In the *GT* article, an Associate Professor, Diao Daming, from the Renmin University of China in Beijing, recommended other countries abide by the primary WHO instructions, which did not require such actions, instead of "blindly following the U.S. move."⁽⁸¹⁾

Other evidence of Chinese propaganda was described in a recently published article appearing in *Forbes*, where it was noted that during the prior year (Jan 2021 – Jan 2022) not one death had been attributed to COVID-19 in the PRC, despite reports of several outbreaks of the infection across China.⁽⁸²⁾

The article disclosed the number of deaths directly attributed to SARS-CoV-2 was only 4,636 since the pandemic started, giving China, the most populace nation on Earth, one of the lowest fatality rates in the world. This "zero death rate" was surprising given the official COVID-19 case statistic for the same period was 16,000 cases nationwide.

When calculated as a death rate per 100,000 people, the Chinese ratio is 0.35 per 100,000, compared to 264 per 100,000 in the U.S. In contrast, warnings by analysts in the C.I.A. estimated China was deliberately underestimating its death rate. A study released by *The Economist*,⁽⁸³⁾ estimated nearly 800,000 deaths, more than 150 times the official CCP number.

The leak of minutes (onto *Weibo*, a Chinese media site) from the Dec 21, 2023, meeting of the China National Health Commission (NHC) reported nearly 37 million COVID cases across the nation on Dec 20, 2023, while the total number of infections dating from December 1-20, 2023 was 248 million individuals, which accounts for more than 18% of the population.⁽⁸⁴⁾

What makes this leak of information so important, furthering the concerns for more Chinese obfuscation regarding the true scope of the viral spread in Mainland China, is that their continued reported death rate remains woefully less than the suspected official tallies.⁽⁸⁴⁾ This data is attributed to Ma Xiaowei, Director of the NHC.

The summary describes genetic sequencing of isolates from affected individuals (1,100) identifying the primary isolates as being of the Omicron subvariants BA.5.2, BF.7 and BM.7. The study found that none of the new viral variants had any significant changes in transmissibility, immune escape, or virulence.⁽⁸⁴⁾

Airfinity, a United Kingdom health data research company, estimated more than 5,000 Chinese were dying from COVID each day from SARS-CoV-2 infection, again, far higher than official statistics (only 5,000 lives since the start of the pandemic). Airfinity calculated that 1.3 to 2.1 million people could die during the current outbreak in China.⁽⁸⁴⁾

Despite these staggering SARS-CoV-2 infection numbers, the CCP has found it fit to lift travel restrictions, a dire development as this will only serve to export and exacerbate Omicron infections in other countries. ⁽⁸⁵⁾

In response, South Korea, Taiwan, Malaysia, India, and Japan will now require COVID testing for any visitors from Mainland China. The Japanese government issued a sharp restriction on flights from and to China.

Leaked reports bypassing CCP censorship describe Chinese hospitals and funeral homes being completely overwhelmed by the increased number of COVID-19 cases across the nation. ⁽⁸⁵⁾

Dr. Howard Bernstein, a physician working at a Beijing hospital was quoted in the article confirming “the hospital has run out of available beds and is overwhelmed from top to bottom.” ⁽⁸⁵⁾

Chinese Foreign Ministry spokesperson, Mao Ning, warned that China will take corresponding measures in response to varying situations “based on the principle of reciprocity,” as reported in *The Global Times*: ⁽⁸⁶⁾

“...we do not believe the entry restriction measures some countries have taken against China are science-based. Some of these measures are disproportionate and simply unacceptable. We firmly reject using COVID measures for political purposes and will take corresponding measures.

China always believes that for all countries, COVID response measures need to be science-based and proportionate. They should not be used for political manipulation, there should not be

discriminatory measures against certain countries, and measures should not affect normal travel and people-to-people exchange and cooperation,” said Mao. ⁽⁸⁶⁾

Western media, in response to the Chinese warnings, cite China’s complete lack of truthfulness and transparency since the start of the pandemic as reasons for the travel restrictions, as well as a lack of information on viral variants and concerns about resurgence of new infections in countries permitting the ready entry of Chinese nationals.

Controversies Swirling Around an Animal Source for COVID-19

Pangolin

Photo credit to Ms. Sarita Jnawali of NTNC – Central Zoo
<https://flickr.com/photos/50838842@N06/29054818144>

In the meantime, controversy still rages over the “source” of SARS-CoV-2.

A report in *Nature News* ⁽⁸⁷⁾ stated researchers at the South China Agricultural University (SCAU) in Guangzhou were promoting the idea that pangolins (Pangolins, sometimes known as scaly anteaters, are mammals of the order Pholidota), animals avidly sought-after in China as a delicacy and for a folk medicinal made from their scales, were the source of SARS-CoV-2 human infection. Even though the animal is under a worldwide ban, and forbidden in China, pangolins are still smuggled from several African and southeast Asian countries. The SCAU scientists reported having isolated a coronavirus in said smuggled animals that was a 99% genetic match to COVID-19. ⁽⁸⁷⁾

However, as it turns out, this “result” did not refer to a sequencing of the viral isolates entire genome, but only to a specific receptor-binding domain (RBD) key to permitting entry of the virus into human cells. ⁽⁸⁸⁾ Xiao Lihua, a parasitologist at SCAU and co-author of the paper, stated the media reports were an “embarrassing miscommunication between the bioinformatics group and the lab group of the study” as the whole-genome side-by-side analysis demonstrated only a 90.3% similarity between the pangolin and SARS-CoV-2.

“Even a 99% similarity between the RBDs of the two viruses is not necessarily enough to link them,” says Linfa Wang, a Duke-national University of Singapore Medical School virologist who was an original member of the scientific team elucidating the origin of SARS-CoV-1. ⁽⁸⁷⁾

Arinjay Banerjee, a scientist who specializes in the study of coronaviruses at McMaster University in Hamilton, Canada, stated: “The genetic similarity should be higher than reported in the study before the host can be identified. The SARS-CoV-1 virus shared 99.8% of its genome

with a civet (a small, lean, mostly nocturnal mammal native to tropical rain forests from tropical Asia and Africa) coronavirus, which is why civets were considered the source.”⁽⁸⁷⁾

The Information Blockade and Silencing of Critics by Media Outlets and Big Tech

Unfortunately, it was not only the CCP propaganda machine clouding the truth surrounding the possible origin and treatment of SARS-CoV-2.

Dr. Robert Malone, a pioneer and researcher in mRNA technologies leading to the development of mRNA vaccines, such as those manufactured by Pfizer, found himself silenced by the social media outlet, LinkedIn in 2021.⁽⁸⁹⁾

“My business pays for LinkedIn premium. I have been deleted,” Malone wrote on Twitter.

“Purchased a service from LinkedIn to promote my company. This is very different from the YouTube or Twitter terms. This arbitrary and capricious action has damaged our business, and we deserve to be compensated.”⁽⁸⁹⁾

According to his spouse, Jill Malone, her husband’s fifteen-year-old personal account was removed without warning or explanation by LinkedIn, a subsidiary of Microsoft.

“Malone explained on Wednesday that the ‘historic record of what I have done, stated, figured out (and when) etc. over time is a key part of establishing my credibility and track record as a professional. But despite this, the account has been erased completely and arbitrarily without warning or explanation,’ he added.”⁽⁸⁹⁾

“In a subsequent tweet, Malone produced an email from a LinkedIn representative, who said that his account violated the firm’s user agreement because he posted ‘misleading or inaccurate information’ about vaccines and COVID-19.”⁽⁸⁹⁾

“[LinkedIn] has provided a list of my thoughtcrimes. An amazing document,” wrote Malone.⁽⁸⁹⁾

Recently, Malone’s concerns voiced to Fox News and other news outlets about giving vaccines to individuals under the age of eighteen were flagged by several so-called “fact-checking” sites. Malone told NTD’s *The Nation Speaks* in late June that heart inflammation reports shift the risk-benefit ratio for children.⁽⁸⁹⁾

“Vaccines save lives. These vaccines have saved lives,” Malone said, adding that he believes the risks associated with mRNA COVID-19 vaccines made by Pfizer and Moderna outweigh the benefits among children.⁽⁸⁹⁾

Speaking to Fox News, Malone stated, “I can say the risk-benefit ratio for those eighteen and below doesn’t justify vaccines, and there’s a pretty good chance that it doesn’t justify vaccination in these very young adults.”⁽⁸⁹⁾

LinkedIn’s move to ban Malone is the latest attempt by a Big Tech firm to curb what they describe as “misinformation” regarding COVID-19 vaccines. Recently, Twitter locked Harvard Medical School epidemiologist Martin Kulldorff’s account after he expressed a skeptical viewpoint on whether masks provide protection.⁽⁸⁹⁾

And early in the pandemic, separately, social media firms suspended the accounts of individuals who questioned the origin of COVID-19 posting it might have emerged from a high-security laboratory in Wuhan, China, in late 2019. ⁽⁸⁹⁾

However, in recent months, U.S. officials, including members of the 17-agency Intelligence Community, have begun to question the official narrative from the Chinese Communist Party and World Health Organization officials, who have claimed the virus was transmitted from animals to humans at a wet market. ⁽⁸⁹⁾

There are many more examples of the arbitrary “silencing” of proponents disseminating information contrary to the mainstream narrative surrounding the COVID-19 epidemic, but they are beyond the scope of this limited review. However, a few more examples bear mention.

Two significant articles aggressively promoting a “natural origins” theory for the SARS-CoV-2 outbreak were published by scientists who formed part of a “response team of experts” recruited by the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, Medicine (NASEM), per a request by a White House official. ⁽⁹⁰⁾

The following reports mentioned in an *Epoch Times* article were employed extensively by mainstream media organizations to push a natural origins theory while discrediting alternative theories—including those that proposed a possible lab leak from the WIV—as “tin foil hat” conspiracy theories.

These reports were part of a coordinated attempt originating from a Feb 1, 2020, teleconference coordinated by Drs. Anthony Fauci, Director of the National Institute of Allergy, and Infectious

Diseases (NIAID), and Jeremy Farrar, Director of the British Wellcome Trust in response to public reporting of potential links between the WIV and SARS-CoV-2. ⁽⁹⁰⁾

After this meeting, any discussions examining SARS-CoV-2 being an accidental laboratory leak from the WIV, were aggressively censored by multiple social media websites, governmental health officials and even the WHO. ⁽⁹⁰⁾

The first publication released as an open letter to the general public was produced on Feb 19, 2020, and was signed by several scientists. An email obtained via a Freedom of Information Act (FOIA) request by the organization, *U.S. Right to Know*, showed that EcoHealth President Peter Daszak (whose organization, EcoHealth, funneled \$3.7 million in funds from Fauci's NIAID, of which at least \$600,000 went to the WIV) drafted the letter demanding "solidarity with all scientists and health professionals in China." ⁽⁹⁰⁾

A second article published on Mar 17, 2020, in the scientific journal, *Nature*, "The Proximal Origin of SARS-CoV-2" ⁽⁹¹⁾ was designed to target experts in medicine, infectious diseases and allied biological fields of study. ⁽⁹⁰⁾

Of the five scientists who are credited as authors of this article, four of them had participated in the infamous Fauci-Farrar teleconference—which was described in an Feb. 1, 2020, email from Farrar as a "discussion ... shared in total confidence." ⁽⁹⁰⁾ ⁽⁹²⁾

Interestingly, one of the scientists who authored the "Proximal Origins" article has since recanted his position. ⁽⁹⁰⁾ ⁽⁹³⁾

The “Proximal Origins” article is notable for two findings that should have immediately raised serious consideration of a laboratory synthesis of SARS-CoV-2: ⁽⁹¹⁾

- 1) The paper states SARS-CoV-2 appears optimized for binding to the human ACE-2 cell receptor.
- 2) The SARS-CoV-2 Spike Protein has a functional polybasic (furin) cleavage site located at the S1-S2 boundary through the insertion of twelve nucleotides into its RNA genome.

It is the second finding, discussed in earlier sections of this review, that should have immediately raised red flags for an artificially modified coronavirus as the furin site **does not exist in any naturally occurring beta-coronavirus ever isolated and identified by researchers.**

A second scientific paper published on Feb 19, 2020, titled “Structure, Function and Antigenicity of the SARS-CoV-2 Spike Glycoprotein” appearing in the journal *Cell* ⁽⁹⁴⁾ stated the following:

“We found that the SARS-CoV-2 S glycoprotein harbors a furin cleavage site at the boundary between the S₁/S₂ subunits, which is processed during biogenesis and sets this virus apart from SARS-CoV-1 and other SARS-related CoVs.” ⁽⁹⁴⁾

It is inconceivable to this author (SES Medina, MD, BS CHE) that a possible artificial origin for SARS-CoV-2 could be so easily swept under the table and labelled “misinformation,” while two reputable scientific papers published very early in the evolution of the COVID-19 worldwide pandemic clearly suggest this after detection of a furin site on the coronavirus Spike Protein, without which it would be impossible for the virus to enter human cells so easily and efficiently.

Additional work published in a paper by Dr. Rossana Segreto from the Department of Microbiology, University of Innsbruck, Austria, (March 25, 2021) ⁽⁹⁵⁾ highlights multiple characteristics possessed by SARS-CoV-2 that make it nearly impossible for the virus to have come from an animal source and was most likely, created in a laboratory. As discussed in Segreto's paper, these include:

- A low rate of evolution in the early phases of transmission (the viral isolates showed an extremely high genetic concordance, meaning there was very little evidence the virus had been circulating for a longer period of time which would have created a more heterogeneous group of similar viruses, instead of the almost pure strain detected in worldwide patient samples. This means there were very few genetic recombinations as seen in any virus that has circulated among many, many sequential hosts).
- An extremely high, efficient pre-existing facility of binding to human angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE-2), the vital binding site necessary for the virus to infect a human cell.
- The existence of the furin cleavage site insert as discussed previously (as a reminder, **there is no example of the furin protein site occurring in nature introduced into a coronavirus such as SARS-CoV-2 via recombination**; however, this artificial coding insertion technique is **identical** to that employed by Drs. Shi at the WIV, and Ralph Baric, at the University of North Carolina. Other published scientific papers have utilized this particular process to introduce arginine codons into viral RNAs thereby inserting furin cleavage sites into the newly synthesized protein). ⁽⁶⁾ It is also important to note that when Dr. Shi of the WIV revealed the sequencing work they had performed on SARS-

CoV-2 for the first time in January 2020, **she showed hundreds of gene sequences of this completely novel virus but stopped short of showing the furin site.** ⁽⁶⁾

- The existence of a fat ganglioside-binding domain in the structure of the Spike Protein which disagrees with the usual host evasion survival mechanisms seen in other human coronaviruses.
- The evidence of an unusually high human and mouse peptide mimicry in the Spike protein structure.
- The proposal that pangolins are the intermediate host for SARS-CoV-2 is unlikely. Although two pangolin coronaviruses discovered ⁽⁹⁶⁾ exhibited potent binding to human ACE-2, the same SP bound ten times weaker to pangolin ACE-2 and binding to a bat ACE-2 (*Rhinolophus ferreus*) was also extremely weak, with almost identical binding affinities for SARS-CoV-2. This suggests that neither of the pangolin coronaviruses had developed a solid adaptation to pangolins, and that the ability of coronaviruses to spread among pangolins will require more investigation.
- In contrast to other species shown to be able to be infected successfully by coronaviruses, pangolins are not trafficked together live and caged together for any extended period of time to permit an exchange of viruses leading to viral enhancement and recombination.
- Pangolins are solitary creatures, critically endangered due to poaching and a lively black market for illegal medicinals, possess limited infection resistance and have been examined in a recent screening of 334 wild pangolins ⁽⁹⁷⁾ that showed these animals have normally no evidence of coronavirus infections.

- There is no existing record showing an early evolutionary adaptation of the SARS-CoV-2 ACE-2 Spike Protein binding domain, which is exceptionally enhanced to bind to human ACE-2.
- The next point bears serious consideration as discussed in Segreto's paper; **bats have been shown to be natural reservoirs of SARS-like viruses, so the binding of SARS-CoV-2 would predictably be extremely high to their native ACE-2 proteins. Instead, bat species exposed to SARS-CoV-2 are very poorly infected by the virus, making it extremely unlikely for them to be the source of COVID-19.**
- In comparison, the association of poor bat susceptibility and an extremely high human adaptation seen in the earliest strains of SARS-CoV-2 contrasts greatly with the viral evolution seen during the MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-1 outbreaks. SARS-CoV-2 was a remarkably good "fit" for infection in humans from the get-go, while poorly suited to infect bats.
- Not only is SARS-CoV-2 the only Beta-Coronavirus (Sarbecovirus) to contain a furin cleavage site, ⁽⁹⁸⁾ no naturally occurring coronavirus with a Spike Protein similarity of more than 40% to SARS-CoV-2 possesses a furin cleavage site.
- The insertion of furin cleavage sites has been an extremely common technique employed in GoF research and can be easily introduced using seamless technology ⁽⁹⁹⁾ ⁽¹⁰⁰⁾ without requiring successive cell passage. The probability of a natural mutation resulting in a segment of twelve amino acids coding for a human-optimized furin cleavage site without any known natural intermediate species in Sarbecovirus is exceedingly low; the introduction of an artificially created furin cleavage site is a far more evolutionary frugal

means of achieving a SARS-CoV-2 highly adapted to human infection without a bat-intermediate host.

- Finally, it is curious that SARS-CoV-2 possesses a fifteen-fold stronger binding affinity for human ACE-2 when compared to SARS-CoV-1. ⁽¹⁰¹⁾

It is amazing to this author how much published research had been done in 2020 during the first full year of the COVID-19 pandemic, and in early 2021, clearly pointing to an artificial source of SARS-CoV-2, yet so many “experts” and commentators in the mainstream media immediately labelled any positions contrary to the “narrative” as “conspiracy theories.”

The accidental release of SARS-CoV-2 theory has been repeatedly attacked as unlikely. Yet a critical review of past incidents in China and other countries where research on dangerous viruses is conducted bear examination.

In his article, “The Good, the Bad and the Ugly: A Review of SARS Lab Escapes” by Gilles Demaneuf, ⁽¹⁰²⁾ he reviews several accidental lab incidents which show the chance of SARS-CoV-2 originating from the WIV being quite tenable.

For example, during the time span of 2003-04, following the limited SARS-CoV-1 outbreak, three separate incidents of laboratory-acquired SARS occurred in just a few months. These were summarized in the WHO SARS Risk Assessment and Preparedness Framework: ⁽¹⁰³⁾

“The first occurred in Singapore involving a researcher at a BSL-3 lab attributed to a breach in safety protocols, followed by a second case from a lab that was part of a military BSL-4 facility in Taipei, then two cases associated with BSL-3 labs in Beijing, involving two researchers which resulted in nine cases; seven of the infected individuals ended up hospitalized with hundreds quarantined.”

An interview with Antoine Danchin, an epidemiologist at the Hong Kong University-Pasteur Research Center, a researcher who specializes in SARS, commenting on the Beijing incidents appeared in *The Scientist* ⁽¹⁰⁵⁾ where he stated:

“Normally, it's not possible to contaminate people even under level two confinement, if the security rules are obeyed, with the appropriate hoods, and so on,” Danchin said. SARS work requires a BSL-3 lab protocol. “So, it suggests there has been some mishandling of something.”

“The lab might have all the right rules, but the people may not comply! For example, notebooks are not supposed to be taken out, a lot of things like that. A virus doesn't jump on people!”

Danchin said.

Despite these, and many other lab leaks, the mainstream media continued to claim any serious examination of the possibility of an accidental lab leak from the WIV as “conspiracy theories.”

In April 2020, *NPR* (National Public Radio) broadcast a story claiming there was “virtually no chance” SARS-CoV-2 was released from the WIV in China, “or anywhere else.” The *NPR* coverage claimed such an “accidental” release “would have required a remarkable series of coincidences and deviations from well-established experimental protocols.” ⁽¹⁰⁵⁾

Donald G. McNeil, Jr., the New York Times Science Writer, reported the possibility that SARS-CoV-2 might have started in a lab located in Wuhan, China, and not as a random, naturally occurring pathogen in an early 2020, 4,000-word piece. However, *The New York Times* declined to publish the piece over “scientific concerns,” the complex thread of facts and evidence, and worries over the political reasons some of the anonymous sources might have had. ⁽¹⁰⁵⁾

In May 2021, *The Washington Post* published five stories on its front pages re-examining the lab leak possibility but used corrected headlines and editor’s notes attached to the prior stories published in 2020. ⁽¹⁰⁵⁾

In a February 2020 article, *The Washington Post* published a story critical of Republican Senator Thomas Cotton’s concerns of a lab leak as a “debunked conspiracy theory.”

However, in May 2021, the *Post* re-worked the Cotton article, ⁽¹⁰⁶⁾ changing “conspiracy theory” to a “fringe theory” and changed the wording of medical experts from “debunking” to “disputed.”

An editorial correction accompanying the re-write stated the *Post* had “inaccurately characterized” Senator Cotton’s remarks, “because, then as now, there was no determination about the origins of the virus.” The *Post*’s Managing Editor, Cameron Barr wrote “questions from readers and others” resulted in a reexamination of the account. ⁽¹⁰⁵⁾

The explanatory news site, *Vox*, amended a story from March 2020, ⁽¹⁰⁷⁾ ridiculing the lab leak story, softening the story’s original assertions, to “clarify the current scientific thinking about a possible lab leak, which has continued to evolve.” ⁽¹⁰⁵⁾

Much of these “about faces” were prompted by a lengthy article by veteran science writer, Nicholas Wade, formerly of *The New York Times*, published in the *Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists* ⁽¹⁰⁸⁾ where he considered the lab leak theory as possible and plausible, worthy of further serious examination.

Wade denounced the CCP, Western scientists and the Mainstream Media for purposely misrepresenting or suppressing vital information about a lab leak, or worse, simply being completely uninterested at investigating the facts. ^{(105) (108)}

Science magazine published an open letter on May 14, 2021, signed by eighteen scientists calling for an “independent investigation” of the COVID lab leak hypothesis. ⁽¹⁰⁹⁾

The scientists wrote: “We must take hypotheses about both natural and laboratory spillovers seriously until we have sufficient data. A proper investigation should be transparent, objective, data-driven, inclusive of broad expertise, subject to independent oversight, and responsibly managed to minimize the impact of conflicts of interest.” ⁽¹⁰⁹⁾

The publication of a story by *The Wall Street Journal* from May 23, 2021, ⁽¹¹⁰⁾ disclosed the declassification of a U.S. Intelligence document contained in a State Department Fact Sheet ⁽¹¹¹⁾ stating three researchers at the WIV had sought medical care in November 2019, several weeks prior to Chinese health officials announcing the SARS-CoV-2 outbreak at the Huanan Wet Market.

Many scientists have questioned the validity of stories circulating in the Mainstream Media doubting the possibility of a lab leak hypothesis to explain the sudden appearance of SARS-CoV-2.

Among them is Bret Weinstein, an evolutionary biologist and Visiting Fellow at the James Madison Program at Princeton University, and co-host of the podcast “*Dark Horse*” who had questioned in July 2021 the reasons for a sudden shift in the media narrative regarding the origin of COVID-19. ⁽¹¹²⁾ Weinstein found the change “mysterious” and “evidence of how corrupt our system has become.”

Weinstein goes on to say, “and it was quite clear to many of us, starting with the tremendous coincidence of this virus having emerged first in Wuhan, **where there is a biosafety level four lab studying these very viruses and enhancing them.** (Author emphasis) It was quite clear that there was at least a viable hypothesis that needed to be discussed.” ⁽¹¹²⁾

Weinstein then says, “before the narrative surrounding the COVID-19 lab leak theory gained traction, those who discussed it were stigmatized, demonized, and portrayed as everything from racist to reactionary. All we were doing was following the evidence. The change in that story, was, I have to say, completely mysterious.”

In *The Epoch Times* article, Weinstein criticized the explanations appearing in the Media for the “about face” on the lab leak theory, particularly by those media outlets that “had gotten the story wrong” as a lab leak possibility gained traction.

As an example, Weinstein cited a May 24, 2021 “correction” by the news outlet, *PolitiFact*, who quietly retracted a September 2020 fact check that labelled a Hong Kong virologist’s claim (Yan Li-meng, PhD, University of Hong Kong School of Public Health) ⁽¹¹³⁾ that SARS-CoV-2 had originally been released from a lab as an “inaccurate” and a “debunked conspiracy theory.” ⁽¹¹⁴⁾

The now-archived “Fact Check” had stated, “The claim is inaccurate and ridiculous. We rate it Pants of Fire!”⁽¹¹⁴⁾ *PolitiFact*, in an updated editor’s note, elaborated on the “reason” it removed the label:

“When this fact-check was first published in September 2020, PolitiFact’s sources included researchers who asserted the SARS-CoV-2 virus could not have been manipulated. That assertion is now more widely disputed. For that reason, we are removing this fact-check from our database pending a more thorough review. Currently, we consider the claim to be unsupported by evidence and in dispute.”⁽¹¹²⁾

Weinstein claimed the lab leak possibility was discarded in “a headlong rush, by all of those who had gotten the story wrong to explain themselves—and their explanations made less than no sense,” in part, because certain journalists and media outlets “seemed to center on the fact that because [former President] Donald Trump had been favorable to the idea that this might have emerged from a lab, that that made it not true, which, of course, is such an illogical conclusion that it’s hard to imagine how anybody who considers himself a journalist could for a moment have been misled. I mean, at worst, if you thought everything that Donald Trump said was a lie—at worst, you would have to take it as no evidence either way. But that’s not how people treated it. They treated it almost as if the truth was always the opposite of what he said.”⁽¹¹⁵⁾

Even *Facebook* has been forced to refrain from “banning” posts suggesting COVID-19 was manmade.⁽¹¹⁶⁾

Dr. Weinstein goes on to state, “it became impossible to maintain the public lie that a laboratory version was somehow in conflict with the evidence.”

“And we now know from Dr. Fauci, his emails, that behind the scenes, the top people didn’t believe it either. They were just simply feeding the public a line that they had their own reasons for wanting the public to believe,” he said.

“I do have hope. But it is contingent on the several different stories that surround COVID revealing to us just how corrupt our system has become.”⁽¹¹²⁾

Most recently, a story published by *The Bitter Winter* website titled, “COVID-19 Origins: 43 Top Security Experts Slam Media for Censoring the Laboratory Hypothesis”⁽¹¹⁷⁾ announced that a group of security experts, among them the new chairman of the U.S. House Foreign Affairs Committee, Michael McCaul, the 27th U.S. National Security Advisor, Robert O’Brien, former Assistant Secretaries of State John Hillen and Christopher Ford, and a cornucopia of prominent university professors specialized in security issues, were concerned by the media coverup. The Vandenberg Coalition, a non-partisan think tank specialized on foreign policy and national security issues, served as the vehicle for this position paper.

Opening with the statement that “COVID-19 has resulted in the loss of an estimated 15 million lives worldwide to date, plus financial losses estimated to be in the tens of trillions globally, including at least \$16 trillion for the United States alone, understanding the origins of the virus is essential to our pandemic preparedness in the future.”⁽¹¹⁷⁾

The signatories of the letter proclaimed: “some editors and reporters of news organizations and scientific publications stifled debate on the origins of the virus. Some even leveled accusations of racism against those who sought in good faith to investigate whether the virus may have originated from a lab leak at the Wuhan Institute of Virology. Leading scientific journals

censored dissenting voices; many science writers at major news outlets promoted narratives or asserted conclusions unsubstantiated by evidence; reporters failed to make even cursory attempts at surfacing potential conflicts of interest of their sources.”⁽¹¹⁷⁾

The letter goes on to say, “by prematurely dismissing or stigmatizing certain questions—from the very outset of the pandemic— many prominent scientists and journalists failed in their duty. Over the past three years, investigations into the origins of COVID-19 have established a lab leak as a legitimate possible explanation for the emergence of the pandemic. These inquiries include the World Health Organization Scientific Advisory Group on the Origin of Novel Pathogens, intelligence reports; letters by scientists; multiple Congressional reports by the [then] minority staffs of the U.S. House Committee on Foreign Affairs and the U.S. Senate Committee on Health, Education, Labor, and Pensions; and inquiries by highly credible scientists and reporters.”⁽¹¹⁷⁾

The signatories offer several examples of such failures, such as the prestigious scientific journal, *The Lancet*, dismissing the laboratory leak hypothesis as a “conspiracy theory,” failing to inform their subscribers that several of the authors of early reports had changed their minds, or when *The New York Times* provided copious publicity for a pre-print version of an article submitted to the journal, *Science*, claiming to unequivocally “debunking” the laboratory hypothesis, yet not thoroughly following up after many of the audacious claims in the article were eliminated following peer review.⁽¹¹⁷⁾

The signatories of the letter do not arrive at any specific conclusion regarding the possibility of a lab leak of a highly genetically engineered virus. However, they do assert the CCP was actively

influencing international media, which included scientific publications, while others possessed an ideological bias, wanting to avoid confrontation with the Chinese. ⁽¹¹⁷⁾

However, the position paper does say the mainstream media and academic publications should be reporting on truthful facts, rather than worrying about the potential political fallout. ⁽¹¹⁷⁾

Other Examples of Coordinated Obfuscation to Suppress the Truth Surrounding the Origins of COVID-19

But it was not only the Mainstream Media and Tech giants who worked to suppress anything that countered the currently accepted “narrative” surrounding the possibility of an accidental lab leak releasing SARS-CoV-2 upon the world. Democrats in the U.S. House of Representatives, via a vote along partisan lines, blocked a bill passed unanimously by the U.S. Senate that would declassify intelligence related to the origins of COVID-19. ⁽¹¹⁸⁾

The Senate bill sponsored by Josh Hawley (R-Missouri) and Michael Braun (R-Indiana) would have required the White House to declassify all intelligence gathered by U.S. agencies looking at the COVID-19 outbreak in China and require the Office of the Director of National Intelligence (ODNI) to “declassify intelligence related to any potential links between the Wuhan Institute of Virology (WIV) and the origins of the COVID pandemic.”

The “COVID-19 Origins Act” had been introduced by House Representatives Michael Burgess (R-Texas), Darin LaHood (R-Illinois), and Brad Wenstrup (R-Ohio) before it was defeated in a 216 to 207 vote.

During his speech on the Senate floor seeking the passage of the Senate bill, Senator Hawley noted “the American people deserve to know about the origins of COVID-19,” adding that some government officials have speculated the virus may have come from the Wuhan Institute of Virology. Hawley continued: “Americans must hold China accountable, whose lies about this virus prevented our country and many others from being able to address it effectively in time.”

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Senator Braun praised the bipartisan nature of their legislation, asking “who disagrees with transparency? China must be held accountable as the virus has ravaged not only the United States, but the world. Why wouldn’t we want to get to the root cause of it?”

The defeat of the bill by the House Democrats occurred just days after the WHO was urging the People’s Republic of China to fully cooperate with a second inquiry into the origins of COVID-19, taking note of the previous difficulties when seeking answers from the CCP when China refused to release raw patient data to the WHO during the first set of investigations in early 2020.

(119) (142) (143)

Finally, it behooves this writer to include examples of direct actions by the CCP in silencing any potential information leaks and reports that could portray the government’s actions during the COVID-19 pandemic in a negative light.

Eva Fu, of the *New Tang Dynasty News Service*, in an article published on August 27, 2021, and updated on September 1, 2021, described efforts by the U.S. State Department to obtain the release of eleven Chinese citizens arrested and detained for releasing information about the COVID-19 pandemic in China to the Chinese-language version of *The Epoch Times*, and publicized their demands that the CCP “cease stifling truthful reporting in China.”⁽¹²⁰⁾

“The United States calls on the PRC (People’s Republic of China) government to release journalists and their contacts detained for their reporting on COVID-19 restrictions and to cease its efforts to silence those who seek to report the truth,” a State Department spokesperson told *The Epoch Times* in an email.⁽¹²⁰⁾

“We consistently underscore the importance of independent, transparent, and fact-based reporting on COVID-19.”⁽¹²⁰⁾

The eleven individuals in question are members of the government-persecuted religious faith group, Falun Gong. They have been confined at the Dongcheng District Detention Center in Beijing since early 2020. A Chinese government indictment released in April 2020 accuses the eleven of “taking photos and uploading them to overseas websites between February and June 2020,” and providing the materials to *The Epoch Times*.⁽¹²⁰⁾

“China needs to stop trying to prevent its citizens from reporting the news and publishing photographs about its COVID-19 restrictions,” comments attributed to Steven Butler, the program coordinator for the *Committee to Protect Journalists*, a press freedom watchdog based in New York City, in an Aug. 24 statement.⁽¹²¹⁾

Via a spokesperson, *The Epoch Times* expressed explicit concerns for the safety of the detainees and made calls to the international community to “condemn this violation of press freedom.”⁽¹²¹⁾

The news organization, *The Epoch Times*, was originally founded in 2000 in the United States as a Chinese-language newspaper, acting as a counter to the CCP’s worldwide propaganda machine. No surprise, *The Epoch Times* has been blocked in China, and many of its earliest reporters have been jailed in China, some for terms as long as ten years.⁽¹²¹⁾

The article reported the “Beijing Dongcheng People’s Court canceled the detainees’ scheduled court appearance on Aug. 19, according to an Aug. 15 post on Minghui.org, a U.S.-based website dedicated to tracking the persecution of Falun Gong.”

The United States Government Connections to the Cover Up Surrounding the Origins of COVID-19

Despite a persistent attempt to deny any involvement by the United States government in possible Gain-of-Function research performed at the WIV, a copious amount of evidence is accumulating that suggest the opposite. As will become clearer in the paragraphs to follow, the Gain-of-Function (GoF) research performed at the WIV was supported both financially and intellectually by the U.S.

The Fauci Connections

In an article published in the UK *Daily Mail* on June 18, 2021, ⁽¹²²⁾ details of secret emails generated by Dr. Anthony Fauci, then Director of the National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID), were obtained and revealed the following details about his response to the emerging SARS-CoV-2 worldwide pandemic:

- *The Daily Mail* reported communications between infectious diseases expert, Kristian Anderson, a Danish evolutionary biologist and professor in the Department of Immunology and Microbiology at the Scripps Research Institute in La Jolla, California, and Dr. Fauci. In a telephone call on January 31, 2020, and in subsequent emails, Anderson expressed concerns to Fauci that his initial examination of genomic sequencing of SARS-CoV-2 raised concerns the virus appeared “engineered.” These emails were apparently shared with other top scientists who also concurred with Anderson that SARS-CoV-2 possessed “unusual features” that implied it looked “engineered.” ⁽¹²²⁾
- The beforementioned email went on to say, “The unusual features of the virus make up a really small part of the genome (<0.1%) so one has to look really closely at all the sequences to see that some of the features (potentially) look engineered.” Anderson went on to add, “the genome was inconsistent with expectations from evolutionary theory.” However, he did add the statement, “those opinions could still change after closer analyses.” ⁽¹²²⁾
- Fauci apparently confirmed to *USA Today* in an interview, that Anderson had expressed those concerns with him, as well as to Jeremy Farrar, Director of the Wellcome Trust, (a

charitable organization founded in 1936 by Henry Wellcome, co-founder of the pharmaceutical giant, Burroughs-Wellcome) who was also on the call.

- The plan, following the call on Jan 31, 2020, was for Anderson to spend the next several weeks looking into the unusual viral sequence, per Fauci.
- Yet surprisingly, by February 4, 2020, Anderson had a dramatic about-face regarding the troubling aspects of SARS-CoV-2, stating in an email that scientists should be “more firm on the question of engineering” and should be “slamming theories” suggesting the virus had been deliberately engineered as “crackpot.”⁽¹²²⁾ The email was sent to scientists composing a letter representing a consensus opinion on behalf of the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering and Medicine, meant for the White House Office of Science and Technology.
- Anderson wrote, “The main crackpot theories going around at the moment relate to this virus being somehow engineered with intent and that is demonstrably not the case.”⁽¹²²⁾
- The *USA Today* article goes on to report Fauci as stating, “Engineering can mean many things and could be done for either basic research or nefarious reasons, but the data conclusively show that neither was done.”⁽¹²²⁾
- Fauci was quoted as saying further, “If one of the main purposes of this document is to counter those fringe theories, I think it's very important that we do so strongly and in plain language consistent with [natural evolution] is a favorite of mine when talking to scientists, but not when talking to the public – especially conspiracy theorists.”⁽¹²²⁾
- In March 2020, Anderson published a paper in the scientific journal, *Nature Medicine*, where he and fellow researchers concluded, “we do not believe that any type of laboratory-based scenario is plausible.”⁽¹²³⁾

- However, the emails released and reviewed by *The Daily Mail* show that Fauci received warnings from several scientific experts in January 2020, February 21, 2020, and on April 16, 2020, that the lab-leak hypothesis was still a real possibility. ⁽¹²²⁾
- *The Daily Mail* coverage revealed on April 18, 2020, that Fauci received an email from the director of a research group partnered with the WIV thanking him for publicly announcing his insistence that there was no credible evidence pointing to the WIV lab as the source of SARS-CoV-2. ⁽¹²²⁾

In a further development, *The Wall Street Journal* reported the existence of a classified document, dated from May 2020, originating from the Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, that revealed their experts were recommending further serious investigation into the possibility of a laboratory leak as the source of SARS-CoV-2. ⁽¹²⁴⁾

According to the *WSJ*, the scientists at the Lawrence Laboratory determined the lab leak hypothesis as “plausible,” and the situation around the virus’s origins “really needed to be looked into carefully.” ⁽¹²⁴⁾

The *WSJ* disclosed that Dr. Fauci points to the February 1, 2020, conference call as proof he “always had an open mind even though I felt then, and still do, the most likely origin (of SARS-CoV-2) was in an animal host.” ⁽¹²⁴⁾

In the same article, White House Chief of Staff, Mark Meadows accused Fauci and the Mainstream Media of “ignoring the facts and siding with China.”

Meadows is quoted further: “What actually should have happened is journalists should have done their job. There was a Pulitzer Prize waiting for somebody to report on it and candidly what

they did is there was so much animosity toward Donald Trump, the president, and his administration they weren't willing to look at the facts.”⁽¹²⁴⁾

In a House Appropriations subcommittee hearing held in late May 2020, Fauci stated the NIAID awarded around \$600,000 in research grants indirectly to the WIV over a timespan of five years to research bat coronaviruses.⁽¹²⁴⁾

However, emails obtained by the conservative watchdog group, *Judicial Watch*, suggested funding for the WIV was more than \$820,000 over six years ending in 2019. This money had been funneled via the non-profit EcoHealth Alliance before the funding was abruptly cut.⁽¹²⁴⁾

This financial backing, and the connections with EcoHealth Alliance will be explored in sections to follow.

In testimony before the House Appropriations subcommittee, Fauci repeatedly insisted that none of the money went towards “Gain of Function” (GoF) research and pushed back at claims he de-emphasized the lab leak theory for “political reasons” and called any criticism of him personally as “attacks on science” in an *MSNBC “Meet the Press”* appearance.⁽¹²⁵⁾

In the televised appearance, Fauci told the host, Chuck Todd, “It's very dangerous, because a lot of what you're seeing as attacks on me, quite frankly, are attacks on science because all of the things that I have spoken about consistently from the very beginning have been fundamentally based on science.”

Further investigations by *Washington Post* columnist, Josh Rogin, revealed Fauci relaunched NIH GoF research without consulting the White House.⁽¹²⁶⁾

Rogin, during an interview on *The Joe Rogan Experience*, elaborated on the reasons why Dr. Fauci, as do many research virologists worldwide, have a vested interest in playing down the possibility of GoF research occurring at the WIV, as that type of scientific investigations may have created SARS-CoV-2, thus resulting in the devastating pandemic which still has the entire world in its grip since the early part of 2020. ⁽¹²⁶⁾

“The Godfather of [gain-of-function virology research], the head of the pyramid, is a guy you may have heard of called Anthony Fauci,” Rogin said. “So, Anthony Fauci, the hero of the pandemic, is the most important person in the world of gain-of-function research there is... Basically, he is the one disbursing all the grants for this, he is the one who pushed to turn it back on after Obama turned it off, that’s another crazy story, he turned it back on without really consulting the White House.” ⁽¹²⁶⁾

“He consulted the Office of Science and Technology Policy, which is part of the White House, but the White House put a pause on it, and he undid the pause,” Rogin continued. “The details are a little sketchy. I’m not saying he did anything necessarily wrong or illegal, but I’m saying that a lot of people that I know inside the Trump administration had no idea that he had turned this back on.” ⁽¹²⁶⁾

Per Rogin, a large portion of the GoF research originally conducted in the U.S. preceding the Obama Administration moratorium in 2014, had been transferred to Chinese laboratories using NIH money funneled through EcoHealth Alliance in 2015, less than one year following the temporary ban. ⁽¹²⁶⁾

Freedom of Information Act Lawsuits Detail NIH Connections to The Wuhan Institute of Virology

Freedom of Information Act (FOIA) lawsuits by the beforementioned *Judicial Watch* obtained the release of over 300 pages of classified emails detailing how the CCP stonewalled in providing timely information about COVID-19, as well as how NIH money was given to Chinese labs, like the WIV, to perform GoF research. ⁽¹²⁷⁾

In the first batch of records obtained (totaling ninety pages), and reviewed by *Judicial Watch*, originating from the Department of Health and Human Services (HHS), the U.S. State Department, and the NIAID, Fauci's agency, there was evidence these agencies knew immediately in January 2020, that the CCP was withholding vital COVID data which hindered an effective risk assessment and response by U.S. public health officials. ⁽¹²⁷⁾

These documents revealed that in April 2018, nearly two years before the deadly coronavirus outbreak, the NIH had dispatched "experts" from their NIH-supported BSL-4 laboratory at the University of Texas Medical Branch, Galveston, Texas, to train WIV technicians in the areas of maintenance and lab management due to the WIV's shortage of properly trained staff. ⁽¹²⁷⁾

As the SARS-CoV-2 outbreak in Wuhan developed steam, Dr. Ping Chen, NIAID's top official in China, sent an email ⁽¹²⁷⁾ to senior NIAID colleagues, Gray Handley, Erik Stemmy, Gayle Bernabe, and Barney Graham with the subject line "PRC Response to Pneumonia Cases Shows Increased Transparency Over Past Outbreaks, but Gaps in Epidemiological Data Remain." Chen writes:

Hi, here is the cable from U.S. Embassy Beijing reporting on the pneumonia outbreak in Wuhan, China. It has ruled out SARS, MERS, and flu. [Redacted] confirmed it is viral infection. [Redacted] The cable contains SBU information. So please don't distribute it widely.

The summary of the cable states:

While PRC officials have released timely and open general information about the outbreak, a lack of epidemiologic data – including an ‘epi curve’ (a summary of dates of onset of illness), characteristics of infected individuals, and other basic epidemiologic information – hinders better risk assessment and response by public health officials. Authorities have also not released information on how they are defining a “case.” Given these gaps in detailed information to-date, and lack of a final confirmed pathogen, the risk to the United States and global health is difficult to assess at this time.

As of January 7, (2020) the Wuhan Health Commission has reported 59 local cases of pneumonia with unknown cause. (Note: Wuhan, a city of approximately 11 million people, is the capital of Central China’s Hubei Province. End note.) According to the Health Commission, some patients are vendors who work in the Huanan Seafood Market, which also sells live exotic animals, including beaver, snakes, porcupines, and deer.

Health officials state there has been no confirmed human-to-human transmission of the disease, and no cases among health workers. Laboratory investigations have ruled out influenza, avian influenza, SARS, MERS, and other common respiratory pathogens, and are awaiting final pathogen results.

PRC [People's Republic of China] officials on December 31, 2019, alerted WHO to the pneumonia outbreak. WHO contacts told Embassy officials that PRC health departments continue to provide information about the outbreak in accordance with WHO's International Health Regulations (IRR). While China has been forthcoming with standard information, WHO contacts note they have not received more detailed and potentially useful information, such as "epi curves" or other epidemiological data. The flow of official PRC information on this outbreak is limited to that coming from the Wuhan Health Commission and National Health Commission. ⁽¹²⁷⁾

“These (and other) FOIA documents show that Fauci’s agency has been hiding information on China’s failure to provide essential data on COVID-19,” per Judicial Watch President Tom Fitton. “The slow-rolling and stonewalling by Fauci’s agency on China, gain of function, and its COVID response generally is pure obstruction.” ⁽¹²⁷⁾

In another FOIA document release, *Judicial Watch* found emails from January 27, 2020, detailing the efforts by a WHO official pushing for a press release, approved by Fauci, strongly supporting China’s COVID-19 response.

A separate successful FOIA lawsuit request, revealed in a December 7, 2021, press release by *Judicial Watch*, suggests HHS approved funding specifically targeting coronaviruses in 2018.

⁽¹²⁸⁾

The documents include grant application descriptions suggestive of GoF research involving RNA extractions from bats, experimentation on coronaviruses, and attempts to create a chimeric

virus as well as an effort to genetically manipulate the full-length bat SARSr-CoV-WIV1 strain molecular clone. (Author underlining) ⁽¹²⁸⁾

One example of this documentation is an email dated January 27, 2020, from NIAID official, David Morens, sent to Chief of Staff, Immediate Office of the Director, NIAID, Greg Folkers in a heavily redacted thread: ⁽¹²⁸⁾

[S]ome background on our support of the EcoHealth group (Peter Daszak et al), which has for years been among the biggest players in coronavirus work, also in collaboration with Ralph Baric, Ian Lipkin, and others. [Redacted].

NIAID has been funding Peter's group for coronavirus work in China for the past 5 years through [grant] R011R01A|110964: "Understanding the Risk of Bat Coronavirus Emergence." That's now been renewed, with a specific focus to identify cohorts of people highly exposed to bats in China and work out if they're getting sick from CoVs....

Collaborators include Wuhan Institute of Virology (currently working on the nCoV) and Ralph Baric. The results of the work to date include:

- *[Redacted]*
- *Discovered Swine Acute Diarrheal Syndrome Virus (SADS-CoV) killing >25,000 pigs in Guangdong Province (Published in Nature)*
- *Found SARS-related CoVs that can bind to human cells (Published in Nature), and that cause SARS-like disease in humanized mouse models.*
- *[Redacted]*

Also, prior to the above R01, Peter's folks worked under an R01 with Eun-Park as Program Officer on viral discovery in bats, and originally identified SARS-CoV as having a likely origin in bats (published in Science).

Chief of Staff, Folkers, then forwards the message to Fauci and others.

Another FOIA records request obtained by *Judicial Watch* was a "Notice of Award" dated July 13, 2020, where the NIH increased grant monies to EcoHealth Alliance (a New York City-based NGO that is working with the University of California Davis), managed by Peter Daszak, by \$369,819 with a project term running from June 1, 2014, through June 30, 2023, for Daszak's project, "Understanding the Risk of Bat Coronavirus Emergence." Per the approval budgeting, Daszak's NGO EcoHealth Alliance was to receive \$712, 441 in each of the years 2019 through 2024 under the grant. ⁽¹²⁸⁾

Of note, in a personal biography section included in the beforementioned grant to EcoHealth Alliance dedicated to the Director of the WIV, Dr. Shi Zhengli, she describes one of her research projects involving "evolution mechanism of the adaption of bat SARS-related coronaviruses to host receptor molecules and the risk of interspecies infection." ⁽¹²⁸⁾

Author Note: isn't that research title interesting. It's almost a clearcut description of a path to developing a SARS-CoV-2-like virus.

Another key participant whose biography is included in the grant application is Professor Ralph Baric, a member of the Departments of Epidemiology, Microbiology, and Immunology at UNC.

Dr. Baric is known worldwide for his seminal work on the development of fundamental genetic, biochemical, molecular, and immunological techniques employed in the study of the molecular mechanisms controlling viral evolution, viral immunity, virus-host interactions and vaccine-mediated protective immunity of coronaviruses, noroviruses and flaviviruses. He is based at the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill campus.

Baric is credited with developing synthetic genomics and reverse genetic protocols used to create molecular coronavirus cDNA clones for SARS-CoV-1, SARS-like bat coronaviruses, MERS, several other non-bat coronaviruses, Dengue virus and Zika virus. His laboratory has spent years working with Drs. Daszak and Shi from the WIV on SARS-CoV.

Dr. Baric has over 314 publications, and he was instrumental in training Dr. Shi in the very laboratory techniques that would permit the development of a virus such as SARS-CoV-2 synthetically. ⁽¹²⁸⁾

Within the FOIA cache (of which an inordinate number of redactions exist in the documents) obtained by *Judicial Watch* was a July 2020 letter from HHS to EcoHealth Alliance which contained the following passages (Author Note – certain phrases are underlined by this writer for emphasis):

[T]he NIH has received reports that the Wuhan Institute of Virology (WIV), a subrecipient of EcoHealth Alliance under R01AI110964, has been conducting research at its facilities in China that pose serious bio-safety concerns and, as a result, create health and welfare threats to the public in China and other countries, including the United States.

We have concerns that WIV has not satisfied safety requirements under the award, and that EcoHealth Alliance has not satisfied its obligations to monitor the activities of its subrecipient to ensure compliance.

Therefore, effective the date of this letter, July 8, 2020, NIH is suspending all activities ... until such time as these concerns have been addressed to NIH's satisfaction. ⁽¹²⁸⁾

Additional funding for research at the WIV, as well as other grants already mentioned, included a five-year allocation by the NIAID (Fauci's department) running from 2019-2024 totaling \$381,505. ⁽¹²⁸⁾

Details of the work to be conducted by the WIV under this latter grant included:

- “Running RNA extractions for 1,000 bats per year (two samples per bat: rectal and blood) in each year of the project.”
- “Support for in vitro experiments using pseudoviruses carrying the spike proteins ... or live viruses in cell lines of different origins, binding affinity assays between the spike proteins ... and different cellular receptor molecules, and humanized mice experiments.”
- “In collaboration with Ralph Baric (UNC), we used the SARS-CoV reverse genetics system ... to generate a chimeric virus with a mouse-adapted SARS-CoV backbone expressing SHC014 S protein with 10% sequence divergence from SARS-CoV S. This chimera replicated in human airway epithelium, using the human ACE2 receptor to enter cells ... Thus, **SARS-CoVs with diverse variants of SL-CoV S protein without**

deletions in the RBD (Receptor Binding Domain) can use human ACE2 as receptor for cell entry.” [Emphasis in original]

- “We aim to expand the known diversity of SARSr-CoVs by over 125 strains, targeting 10-25% S protein divergence that we predict infers high spillover risk and evasion of immune therapeutic and vaccine efficacy.”
- **“We will ... construct chimeric SARSr-CoVs using the WIV1 backbone, and these S genes as done previously. Construction of chimeric SARSr-CoV viruses: infectious clones with the S gene of novel SARSr-CoVs and the SARSr-CoV WIV1 genome backbone using the reverse genetic system developed in our previous R01.”** (Author emphasis added)
- In a section of the grant request titled, “P3CO Research” (P3CO stands for Potential Pandemic Pathogen Care and Oversight), the applicants wrote: “Recognizing the implementation of new gain of function research guidelines under P3CO, SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV are subject to these guidelines, and as such, reverse genetic studies are subject to review ... **Importantly, we are not proposing to genetically manipulate SARS-CoV** over the course of this proposal. However, we are proposing to genetically manipulate the full-length bat SARSr-CoV WIV1 strain molecular clone during the course of the proposal, which is not a select agent, has not been shown to cause human infections, and has not been shown to be transmissible between humans.” [Emphasis in original]

Judicial Watch President, Thomas Fitton commented regarding these FOIA releases: “These records are proof positive that U.S. tax dollars were dishonestly used by Fauci’s agency to fund ‘gain of function’ coronavirus research.”⁽¹²⁸⁾

Another separate set of FOIA publications was obtained by *The Intercept* ⁽¹²⁹⁾ which included two previously unpublished grant proposals funded by NIAID.

The Intercept article quotes Gary Ruskin, Executive Director of U.S. Right to Know, a group that has been aggressively investigating the possible origins of COVID-19: “This is a road map to the high-risk research that could have led to the current pandemic.” ⁽¹²⁹⁾

The first grant of interest has been discussed above, “Understanding the Risk of Bat Coronavirus Emergence.” However, *The Intercept* article highlights a critical detail about the viral research conducted in Wuhan: **key experimental laboratory work with humanized mice was conducted at a biosafety level 3 (BSL-3) lab at the Wuhan University Center for Animal Experimentation, and not at the WIV, as assumed in the past. Work on any virus such as a genetically modified SARS-CoV must be performed in a BSL-4 lab to minimize the potential for an accidental release of such a modified virus.** (Author emphasis)

The Intercept goes on to say these uncovered documents raise additional concerns about the theory that the pandemic may have indeed started as a lab accident, a proposal vehemently dismissed by Dr. Daszak, Director of EcoHealth Alliance. ⁽¹²⁹⁾

The article from *The Intercept* highlights comments by molecular biologist, Alina Chan, from the Broad Institute, a research organization operated by M.I.T. and Harvard, who upon reviewing these grant proposals, thought Daszak’s EcoHealth Alliance had reason to take the lab leak theory seriously: ⁽¹²⁹⁾

“In this proposal, they actually point out that they know how risky this work is. They keep talking about people potentially getting bitten—and they kept records of everyone who got

bitten,” Chan said. “Does EcoHealth have those records? And if not, how can they possibly rule out a research-related accident?”⁽¹²⁹⁾

Another molecular biologist, Richard Ebright, from Rutgers University, after reviewing the FOIA documents commented how critical information about the creation of novel viruses at the WIV was described:

“The viruses they constructed were tested for their ability to infect mice that were engineered to display human type receptors on their cell,” Ebright wrote to *The Intercept* after reviewing the FOIA dossier.

Ebright also said the documents make it clear that two different types of novel coronaviruses were able to infect humanized mice. “While they were working on SARS-related coronavirus, they were carrying out a parallel project at the same time on MERS-related coronavirus,” Ebright said, referring to the virus that causes Middle East Respiratory Syndrome.⁽¹²⁹⁾

EcoHealth Alliance Commits Research Grant Violations

A recent article published in *The Epoch Times* on January 13, 2022,⁽¹³⁰⁾ describes a review by the NIH of EcoHealth Alliance which found the non-profit committed a “slew of violations.” The letter had been made public by Republican lawmakers on the House Oversight Committee.

The article states Dr. Michael Lauer, a Deputy Director at the NIH, found EcoHealth was non-compliant with eight different portions of a written agreement it entered into with the U.S. government, failing to permit access to the WIV's laboratory records and financial statements, failing to report inventions created at the research site, and failed to certify requirements imposed by NIH to ensure the funding was employed in accordance with U.S. laws and regulations. ⁽¹³⁰⁾

The letter, addressed to Dr. Peter Daszak, EcoHealth's Chief of Staff and president, and Dr. Aleksei Chmura, stated, "EcoHealth has demonstrated a history of failure to comply with several elements of the terms and conditions of grant awards not only for these active awards, but also for the suspended award, R0AI110964." ⁽¹³⁰⁾

Apparently, the NIH had previously suspended a single grant to EcoHealth but permitted the agency to receive funds via other awards despite its links with the WIV.

NIH Funds Gain-of-Function Experimentation in China

This prior disclosure adds urgency when examined and added to additional files obtained in October 2021, by the same Oversight Committee. Following a thorough review by a panel of scientific experts, they concluded U.S.-funded experimentation at the WIV included gain-of-function research on modified bat viruses, contrary to assertions by Dr. Anthony Fauci of the NIAID. ⁽¹³¹⁾

The October 2021 disclosure revealed an experiment conducted at the WIV comparing mice infected with a bat coronavirus to mice infected with a modified strain created by researchers. (Author emphasis)

Lawrence Tabak, the Principal Deputy Director at the NIH, told Republican lawmakers in letters dated from Oct. 20, 2021, that the experimental mice infected with the modified version “became sicker than those infected” with the original version. ⁽¹³¹⁾

In the same *Epoch Times* article, Dr. Richard Ebright commented in his Twitter account that “the NIH corrects untruthful assertions by NIH Director Collins and NIAID Director Fauci that NIH had not funded gain-of-function research in Wuhan.” ⁽¹³¹⁾

The “limited experiment” was aimed at seeing if “spike proteins from naturally occurring bat coronaviruses circulating in China were capable of binding to the human ACE2 receptor in a mouse model,” Tabak wrote, adding that the “unexpected result” was not “something that the researchers set out to do.” ⁽¹³¹⁾

Several scientists asserted in the article, whether intended or not, the research fit the definition of gain-of-function. ⁽¹³¹⁾ (Author emphasis)

“The genetic manipulation of both MERS and the SARS conducted in Wuhan clearly constituted gain-of-function experiments,” Jonathan Latham, executive director of The Bioscience Research Project, told *The Epoch Times* in an email. “Further, it is absurd of NIH to describe the enhanced viral pathogenicity observed in the experiments they funded as ‘unexpected,’ when clearly these experiments were expressly designed to detect increased pathogenicity.” ⁽¹³¹⁾

To make matters worse, the article goes on to describe an EcoHealth final report describing experiments conducted on clones of MERS-CoV, the virus that caused an outbreak in the Middle East in 2012, possessing a mortality rate of up to 35%, many times that of SARS-CoV-2. ⁽¹³¹⁾ (Author emphasis)

Rep. James Comer (R-Ky.), ranking Republican on the House Oversight and Reform Committee, told *The Epoch Times* in an email, “Thanks to the hard work of the Oversight Committee Republicans, we now know that American taxpayer dollars funded gain-of-function research at the Wuhan lab.” ⁽¹³¹⁾

Gary Ruskin, Executive Director of U.S. Right to Know, told *The Epoch Times*, “These fresh disclosures add to the concerns about so-called government transparency.” ⁽¹³¹⁾

“It has been obvious for decades that our federal government is not transparent enough, that there is not nearly enough congressional oversight, and that the Freedom of Information Act (FOIA) badly needs strengthening. We citizens need better transparency tools to uncover all sorts of corruption, mismanagement, waste, fraud, abuse of power, and impending disasters,” said Ruskin, adding that the NIH has an “abysmal” track record of being transparent. ⁽¹³¹⁾

S.T. Karnick, Publications Director at The Heartland Institute, an American conservative and libertarian public policy think tank, was quoted in same *The Epoch Times* article as stating, “Even if the research EcoHealth conducted under the National Institutes of Health grant does not precisely fit the definition of gain-of-function, which is for scientists and not policy analysts to decide, government transparency certainly required the NIH to reveal this information at the very beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic. At this point, it is obvious the NIH and other government

health agencies require reform and far more intensive oversight by Congress, and in some cases outright abolition.”⁽¹³¹⁾

“The experiments are overly risky,” said Jack Nunberg, a virologist, and Director of the Montana Biotechnology Center at the University of Montana. This concern was echoed by Jonathan Latham, Executive Director of The Bioscience Research Project, who felt “the experiments clearly constitute gain-of-function.”⁽¹³¹⁾

Synthesis: Is It Possible the Wuhan Institute of Virology Was the Source of SARS-CoV-2? A Summary of the Evidence

The Chinese Surveillance State

The People’s Republic of China (PRC), governed by the Chinese Communist Party (CCP), is the most powerful and oppressive police state in the world, empowered by a pervasive AI (artificial intelligence) computer system interconnected from the national government level down to the local precinct. It has a nationwide facial recognition software used to watch its civilian population anywhere a surveillance video camera is located. It renders the famous “telescreen” technology employed in the dystopian novel, “1984” by George Orwell, childishly inadequate by comparison in its ability to track Chinese citizens in all walks of life.

Since the CCP seized power in 1949, it employed human informants early on to monitor its own citizens. But in 2005, the Chinese government created a mass surveillance system called Skynet.

(132)

Skynet employs over 20 million cameras, some placed outside mosques in the Xinjiang region, in temples located in Tibet, and even in the homes of dissidents.

In 2017, the CCP started using various mobile phone apps to broaden their ability to surveil their citizenry, stating the apps were for national security purposes and to permit citizens to report violations. (133)

After 2018, mass camera surveillance became the most notable upgrade, with the CCP installing them on streets, adding them to internet services, and introducing newly invented surveillance methods based on social credit and identity. (134) (135)

With the installation of these mass camera surveillance systems in 2018 came the incorporation of facial recognition technology, surveillance drones, robot police and data collection looking at online social media platforms to better monitor its citizenry. (136)

Industry research company, HIS Markit, estimates that by the end of 2019, 770 million surveillance cameras existed worldwide, with 416 million in China alone. It is estimated that if these trends continue, by 2021-23 there will be 540 million cameras in China, watching its populace. The CCP declares publicly these extreme measures are intended to prevent crime, but ordinary citizenry is concerned their personal data and privacy has been sacrificed. (137)

Now in 2022-23, the CCP employs social media platforms like Weibo (China's version of Twitter, with over 570 million users) to record and display a user's exact location using their IP

address. Per the website, this information is used to “maintain a healthy and orderly atmosphere for discussion,” and to “ensure the authenticity and transparency of content.”⁽¹³⁸⁾

WeChat, another Chinese social media platform, also displays location data on all users.⁽¹³⁹⁾

These social media platform softwares can track the user’s location 24 hours a day continuously.

Per the CCP, this technology is being employed to “combat ‘bad behavior’”⁽¹⁴⁰⁾ ⁽¹⁴¹⁾

"In order to reduce undesirable behaviors such as impersonating parties, malicious rumors ... as well as to ensure the authenticity and transparency of the disseminated content, the site launched the 'IP Territory' function in March this year," announced the social media platform's official account in Chinese.

Why all this discussion about the Chinese surveillance police state? Because it exemplifies how tightly information and freedom of information dissemination is controlled in the PRC, thus preventing any reliable data on COVID-19 and its origin from emerging until the CCP is no longer in power. Despite all efforts, this absolute control of information (and the silencing of informants) will keep the definitive origins of SARS-CoV-2 wrapped in mystery.

Miscellaneous Facts Regarding the SARS-CoV-2 Pandemic

- Millions of Chinese citizens were permitted to freely travel the country until a nationwide quarantine by the CCP was instituted on January 23, 2020, almost a month after the first cases of a strange pneumonia appeared in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China.⁽³⁾

- It is estimated the CCP permitted five million travelers to fly out of the Wuhan International Airport before the Jan 23rd quarantine. ⁽³⁾
- The top ten destinations for these air travelers were: Japan, Thailand, Hong Kong, South Korea, Taiwan, Malaysia, Vietnam, the United States, Singapore, and Australia. ⁽³⁾
- The CCP and the international scientific community announced the virus was natural in origin, jumping from bats, via another animal host, to humans, spreading from a contaminated animal sold at the Wuhan/Huanan Wet Market (WWM), where both live and dead animals are purchased for food and folk medicinals. ⁽⁴⁾
- However, the CCP has produced no evidence to support a natural emergence explanation. ⁽⁴⁾
- Both SARS-CoV-1 and MERS viruses left copious traces of their origin in the environment. The intermediate host for SARS-CoV-1 (civets) was identified within four months of the outbreak, and the host of MERS (camels) in nine months.
- **Since the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic started, Chinese researchers have neither determined the original source bat population, or the intermediate animal species to which SARS-CoV-2 jumped, nor serological evidence that any identified, Chinese residents, including the people of Wuhan, had ever been exposed to SARS-CoV-2 before the fall of 2019.** ^{(4) (5) (6) (142)} (Author emphasis)
- A serendipitous inventory of the animals (47, 381 individuals from thirty-eight species which included thirty-one protected species) sold at all seventeen wet market shops at the WWM, published in *Nature*, ⁽⁷⁾ was performed between May 2017 and November 2019. No pangolins (a scaly anteater and a primary suspect for an intermediate host) or bats were traded.

- The two closest relatives of SARS-CoV-2 were collected from bats living in caves located in Yunnan, 1500 kilometers from Wuhan. If the virus had first infected inhabitants in Yunnan, it would have confirmed a natural spillover into humans detectable in cases occurring in the intervening provinces between Yunnan and Hubei. That didn't happen. ⁽⁴⁾

General Points of Fact Surrounding COVID-19

- On May 2020, the director of the Wuhan Institute of Virology (WIV), Wang Yanyi declared SARS-CoV-2 “was significantly different from any live pathogen studied at the institute, and that there was no chance it leaked from their laboratories.” ⁽⁷⁾
- During the same interview, Wang stated she no longer had samples of a coronavirus (RaTG13) discovered in a Yunnan Province cave bat back in 2013, which the WIV scientists determined to be a 96.2% genetic match to SARS-CoV-2. ⁽⁷⁾ How convenient!
- In addition, Gao Fu, director of the Chinese CDC, declared in official state media that no animals sold at the WWM had been linked to the virus's spread to humans. ⁽⁷⁾
- A U.S. Department of State Fact Sheet, published in January 2021 ⁽⁸⁾, affirmed several WIV researchers fell ill in autumn 2019, before the first identified cases of SARS-CoV-2. ⁽⁸⁾

CCP Cover-Up Documentation

- The State Department documented the CCP's activities preventing independent journalists, investigators, or global health authorities to interview any scientists at the WIV, as well as those who reportedly fell ill during autumn 2019. ⁽⁸⁾
- Chinese authorities repeatedly put roadblocks hampering the free flow of information from the very start of the growing medical crisis.
- Dr. Li Wenliang, the first physician to sound the alarm of a new, lethal virus suddenly appearing in Wuhan, was forced by the local police to sign a statement admitting that his warning constituted "illegal Behavior." He later died from COVID-19 contracted from patients he treated. ⁽⁵⁹⁾
- The CCP ordered news websites to silence notifications alerting readers of his untimely death, removing Li's name from trending topics pages, and ordering hundreds of fake online commentators to inundate social sites with extraneous chatter, emphasizing "discretion." ⁽⁶⁵⁾
- A Wuhan police crackdown began with an announcement of an investigation of eight individuals for spreading "rumors." ⁽⁵⁹⁾
- The Wuhan Health Commission, as a response to the "rumors," announced twenty-seven people were sick from a pneumonia of unknown cause. The official statement declared "there was no reason to be alarmed." ⁽⁵⁹⁾
- In the weeks to follow, Chinese authorities systematically silenced physicians and other Wuhan residents for raising concerns about the increasing number of new cases. They minimized the dangers to the public, thus preventing individuals from taking any

meaningful measures to protect themselves. It was this stonewalling of the dissemination of vital information that led public health experts to say the Chinese government stymied one of its best opportunities to prevent the emergence of an epidemic. ⁽⁵⁹⁾

- Wuhan political officials used unusual optimism to announce at this time that their “efforts” had stopped the virus at its source as the cluster of ill patients was limited, and the proclaimed “there was no evidence the virus spread between humans.” ⁽⁵⁹⁾
- On Jan 8, 2020, the E.R. at Hospital No. 5 was overflowing with patients suffering from the “unknown” illness, with many of the cases occurring in family clusters, all during the “no human-to-human spread” declarations of the Wuhan health officials. ⁽⁵⁹⁾
- However, on Jan 13, 2020, the first case was reported in Thailand, confirming the spread of the virus outside China’s national borders. ⁽⁵⁹⁾
- During the third week of January, Wuhan celebrated an annual, massive potluck reception for over 40,000 families, clear evidence of the lackadaisical approach local leaders took of the outbreak. ⁽⁵⁹⁾
- PRC President, Xi Jinping, did not officially address the coronavirus outbreak publicly until Jan 20, 2020. ⁽⁶⁰⁾
- Why did spending on PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction) equipment and supplies, a key technology employed in the detection of illnesses such as SARS-CoV-2, soar several months before the first official reporting of COVID-19 cases? ⁽⁶¹⁾
- The cybersecurity firm, Internet 2.0, an Australian entity, tracking the sales of PCR testing machines and kits over several years, observed a nearly 50% increase between 2018 to 2019—the year before the COVID-19 outbreak spread across the world,

implying a possibility that COVID-19 was already in circulation among Chinese communities during the summer of 2019, long before public recognition by the CCP. ⁽⁶¹⁾

- The investigation revealed a “notable, significant and abnormal” number of PCR equipment procurements in 2019 by Wuhan-based entities like the People’s Liberation Army Airborne Army Hospital, (May 2019), the WIV (November 2019), the Wuhan University of Science and Technology (October 2019) and finally, the Hubei Province Districts Centers for Disease Control and prevention (May-December 2019). ⁽⁶²⁾
- **There currently is no official explanation by the PLA nor the CCP for the reasons behind these unusual and inherently suspicious procurements.** (Author emphasis)
- For Chinese social media platforms and news websites, CCP censors ordered: “... do not use push notifications, do not post commentary, do not stir up speculation. Safely control the fervor in online discussions, do not create hashtags, gradually remove from trending topics, strictly control harmful information.” ⁽⁶⁵⁾
- These orders, and thousands of secret Chinese government directives and other pertinent documents had been reviewed by *The New York Times* and *ProPublica* investigative reporters. They show the existence of elaborate systems employed by the CCP to mold and influence online information about the pandemic. ⁽⁶⁵⁾
- Although it is well-known the CCP makes no secret of its rigid internet controls, these documents reviewed by *The New York Times* and *ProPublica* delineate the depth of the behind-the-scenes efforts exercised by Chinese central authorities in maintaining a steel-grip on the dissemination of information.
- Per *The New York Times* piece, “China has a politically weaponized system of censorship; it is refined, organized, coordinated, and supported by the state’s resources,”

said Xiao Qiang, a research scientist at the School of Information at the University of California, Berkeley, and the founder of the *China Digital Times*. “It’s not just for deleting something. They also have a powerful apparatus to construct a narrative and aim it at any target with huge scale. This is a huge thing,” he added. “No other country has that.”⁽⁶⁵⁾

- Xi Jinping, General Secretary of the CCP Central Committee, Chairman of the Central Military Commission, and President of the PRC, ordered the creation of the Cyberspace Administration in 2014 to centralize the control of internet censorship and propaganda. Cyberspace reports directly to the CCP Central Committee.⁽⁶⁵⁾
- To control the evolving crisis, President Xi reshuffled leadership in Hubei province, which contains Wuhan, installing protégés willing to strictly follow the CCP propaganda goals.⁽⁶⁶⁾
- The CCP lobbied the WHO to decline declaring the Wuhan epidemic as a global health emergency, thereby discouraging efforts by other countries to develop coherent, cooperative strategies to contain and stop the spread of SARS-CoV-2.⁽⁶⁷⁾
- The CCP blocked the release of the genome (genetic makeup) of SARS-CoV-2 for more than a week after three separate government laboratories had fully sequenced the virus. The iron fisted grip of information by the CCP was to blame.⁽⁶⁸⁾
- The genome was finally released by the CCP only after another lab published it on a virologist’s website on Jan 11, 2020. To make matters worse, the CCP withheld vital patient and case information for another two weeks.⁽⁶⁸⁾
- The time delay between the initial sequencing by a Chinese government lab on Jan 2, 2020, and the day the WHO finally declared a global health emergency on Jan 30, 2020,

allowed the viral outbreak spread to increase 200-fold, per a retrospective infection data analysis by the Chinese CDC. ⁽⁶⁸⁾

- This purposeful delay prevented recognition of the spread of SARS-CoV-2 to other countries, as well as the concurrent development of testing protocols and devices, antiviral drugs, and possible vaccines. The paucity of clinical patient data also made it impossible to gauge the speed of pathogen spread.
- According to an *AP/NBC News* story, the WHO hotly debated the possibility of limited human-to-human transmission. However, publicly the WHO backtracked, tweeting “preliminary investigations conducted by the Chinese authorities have found no clear evidence of human-to-human transmission”—a statement that later became fuel for critics. ⁽⁶⁸⁾
- In continuation of the CCP propaganda blitz, the Chinese *Global Times* (GT), an English-language daily tabloid newspaper under the control of the Chinese Communist Party’s flagship newspaper, *The People’s Daily*, published multiple stories blaming the appearance of SARS-CoV-2 on other countries introducing the virus to China. ^{(69) (70) (71)}
- In addition, there was evidence of cases not related to the Huanan Wet Market occurring earlier than the official CCP December 2019-January 2020 timeline. One patient was reported in *The Lancet* ⁽⁷²⁾ whose symptoms started on December 1, 2019, and had no association with the wet market.
- *The South China Morning Post* described nine cases occurring in November 2019, listing their age and sex, none of which could be labelled as “patient zero.” ⁽⁷³⁾

- In an interview with a Professor Yu Chuanhua of the Wuhan University published in the *Health Times*, he described two cases from mid-November and one suspected case from September 29, 2019, that were entirely consistent with infection by SARS-CoV-2. ⁽⁷⁴⁾
- Following Professor Yu's interview, the Chinese CDC disseminated an order absolutely forbidding the distribution and release of any information about the SARS-CoV-2 epidemic sans official approval. ⁽⁷⁵⁾ As a result, Yu re-contacted the *Health Times* to say the earlier cases could not be confirmed to have been COVID-19. ⁽⁷⁴⁾
- This proclamation by the China CDC was further broadened and strengthened by an order issued by the PRC's State Council, requiring ALL publications related to COVID-19 be pre-approved by the government entity before release to the public. ⁽⁷⁶⁾
- Another coordinated attempt to snuff out any evidence of the SARS-CoV-2 epidemic starting earlier than the official timeline narrative, was a joint WHO-China position paper dismissing all reported cases of COVID-19 prior to December 8, 2019, and pushed the theory that SARS-CoV-2 came from the Huanan Wet Market, despite a lack of firm scientific data supporting the contention. ⁽⁷⁷⁾
- An extremely serious documented obfuscation by the CCP in their propaganda war and information suppression was an article published in the *South China Morning Post* describing **an official government proclamation ordering every unauthorized Chinese labs to immediately destroy all coronavirus samples collected during the early part of the epidemic, reportedly for "laboratory biological safety."** ⁽⁷⁹⁾ (Author emphasis)
- **The deliberate destruction of these early viral samples would be considered "obstruction of justice" in any legal investigation.**

- Further evidence of pervasive Chinese propaganda was described in an article published in *Forbes*, where it was noted that during the prior year (Jan 2021 – Jan 2022) not one death in China had been attributed to COVID-19, despite reports of several outbreaks of the infection across the country. ⁽⁸²⁾
- Airfinity, a United Kingdom health data research company, estimates that more than 5,000 Chinese are dying from COVID each day from the SARS-CoV-2 2022-2023 outbreak, again, far higher than official statistics (only 5,000 lives since the start of the pandemic). Airfinity calculates that possibly 1.3 to 2.1 million people could die during the current 2023 outbreak in China. ⁽⁸⁴⁾
- Recently, the WHO ceased a second attempt in February 2023 ⁽¹⁴²⁾ to investigate the origin of COVID-19 after the CCP denied them access to relevant sites in China. In an article published in *Nature News*, Maria Van Kerkhove, an epidemiologist at the WHO in Geneva, Switzerland, said, “There is no phase two.” The WHO planned for work to be done in phases, she explained, but “that plan has changed. The politics across the world have really hampered progress on understanding the origins.” This is still more evidence of the continued stonewalling by the CCP squelching any serious scientific investigation to elucidate the origin of SARS-CoV-2. The work planned by WHO scientists included efforts to capture bats in China to see if there were any other wild-type bat viruses closely related to SARS-CoV-2, experimental studies to seek an intermediate animal host for the pathogen, and the testing of stored wastewater and blood samples collected around the world in 2019 and 2020. The earlier WHO report released in March 2021 dismissed as “extremely unlikely” that SARS-CoV-2 had originated from a laboratory. Despite this latter statement supporting the official Chinese position on the origin of COVID-19, CCP

officials rejected the WHO plans, taking issue with the report still stating that a lab-leak could have caused the pandemic. ⁽¹⁴²⁾

- However, in an article published in *US News & World Report* in February 2023, Van Kerkhove said reports stating the WHO had completely abandoned its scientific investigation of the origin of COVID-19 were incorrect. “This is an error in reporting, which is really quite concerning because it's causing some headlines that are inaccurate,” Van Kerkhove explained during a press briefing. “I think we need to be perfectly clear that the WHO has not abandoned studying the origins of COVID-19. We have not, and we will not, and there was no quiet shelving of any plans,” adding that plans were “updated” instead. “Initially, phase two was a plan to be a continuation of that January 2021 mission to Wuhan, which was in a sense seen as phase one, but we updated our plans.” She said that “in a sense” phase two became the permanent establishment of the Scientific Advisory Group for the Origins of Novel Pathogens, which she said “was, in effect, our best effort to move this work forward.” ⁽¹⁴³⁾
- Van Kerkhove added, “the WHO will follow all hypotheses, follow any science that leads us in any direction.” ⁽¹⁴³⁾
- The Associate Director of the National Emerging Infectious Diseases Laboratory Institute at Boston University in Massachusetts, Gerald Keusch, says the origins investigation was “poorly handled by the global community. It was poorly handled by China. It was poorly handled by the WHO.” The WHO should have been relentless in creating a positive working relationship with the Chinese authorities, says Keusch; if it was being stonewalled, it should have been honest about that. ⁽¹⁴²⁾

The Search for an Animal Source Spreading SARS-CoV-2

- The Huanan Wet Market was closed on January 1, 2020, and several investigations followed, including environmental sampling, as well as sampling of frozen animal carcasses at the market. **Of the 336 samples collected from animals, none were PCR-positive for SARS-CoV-2.** ⁽²⁶⁾ (Author emphasis)
- Sixty-nine out of 842 environmental samples were positive by PCR for SARS-CoV-2. Sixty-one of those (88%) were from the western wing of the market. Of these, twenty-two samples were from eight different drains and sewage, and three viruses were isolated, sequenced and shared on GISAID. These were virtually identical to the patient samples collected at the same time (>99.9 % homology). ⁽²⁶⁾
- In comparison, the ninety-one civets and fifteen racoon dogs tested (in January 2004) for SARS-CoV-1 from wet markets located in Guangdong Province, China, as sources for the virus were 100% positive, with all 106 animals harboring the pathogen. ⁽²⁷⁾
- The testimony of thirty-one residents and twenty-eight visitors to the Huanan Wet Market confirm the local populace does not eat bats as part of their diet. ⁽⁵⁷⁾
- If the search for a zoonotic source for COVID-19 is entertained, the most closely related family of bat coronaviruses (Beta coronaviruses) to SARS-CoV-2 are in Yunnan Province in Southwestern China, 1900 km away from Wuhan. ⁽⁶⁾
- **The flight range of bats is estimated around 50 km. For a bat-derived COVID-19 precursor virus to make its way from Yunnan to Hubei province directly, without first infecting many victims along the way, is highly unlikely as no reports of any**

SARS-CoV-2 infections in the intervening provinces were made prior to the Wuhan outbreak. ⁽⁶⁾ (Author emphasis)

- A report in *Nature News* ⁽⁸⁷⁾ stated researchers at the South China Agricultural University (SCAU) in Guangzhou promoted the idea that pangolins (Pangolins, sometimes known as scaly anteaters, are mammals of the order Pholidota), animals avidly sought-after in China as a delicacy and for a folk medicinal made from their scales, were the source of SARS-CoV-2 human infection. Even though the animal is under a worldwide ban, and forbidden in China, pangolins are still smuggled from several African and southeast Asian countries.
- The SCAU scientists reported having isolated a coronavirus in said smuggled animals that was a 99% genetic match to COVID-19. ⁽⁸⁷⁾
- However, as it turns out, this “result” did not refer to a sequencing of the viral isolates entire genome, but only to a specific receptor-binding domain (RBD) key to permitting entry of the virus into human cells. ⁽⁸⁸⁾
- Xiao Lihua, a parasitologist at SCAU and co-author of the paper, said the media reports were an “embarrassing miscommunication between the bioinformatics group and the lab group of the study” as the whole-genome side-by-side analysis demonstrated only a 90.3% similarity between the pangolin and human coronaviruses.
- Arinjay Banerjee, a scientist who specializes in the study of coronaviruses at McMaster University in Hamilton, Canada, stated: “The genetic similarity should be higher than reported in the study before the host can be identified. The SARS-CoV-1 virus shared 99.8% of its genome with a civet (a small, lean, mostly nocturnal mammal native to

tropical rain forests from tropical Asia and Africa) coronavirus, which is why civets were considered the source.”⁽⁸⁷⁾

CCP Bioweapons Program Facts

- The U.S. has publicly complained about the CCP’s past biological weapons work, despite China’s obligations under the Biological Weapons Convention, and has determined the WIV engaged in classified, secret projects with the Chinese military.⁽⁸⁾⁽⁹⁾
- **May 7, 2021, the news site, *The Australian*, reported the existence of a 2015 publication by the Chinese military that openly discussed the potential weaponization of SARS coronaviruses.**⁽¹⁰⁾ (Author emphasis)
- Contained within that position paper were predictions by Chinese military scientists and senior public health officials that should World War III materialize, it would be decided by employing newly developed biological weapons, not through the use of conventional arms or nuclear weapons.⁽¹⁰⁾
- The military position paper was consistent with prior evidence of offensive Chinese biowarfare research using advanced technologies such as gene-editing and viral gain of function (GoF).⁽¹⁰⁾
- It is also true that academics and senior officers in the Chinese People’s Liberation Army (PLA) have openly discussed the importance of examining the military potential as well as offensive applications for biotech.⁽¹²⁾⁽¹³⁾

- General Zhang Shibo, a past president of the PLA's National Defense University, writes in his book, *New Highland of War*, that **current biotech advances could allow for the creation of new, synthetic pathogens** (Author emphasis) that would be “more toxic, more contagious, and more resistant.”⁽¹²⁾⁽¹⁸⁾
- The French agreed to help set up a BSL-4 lab at the WIV starting in 2004. The project was vigorously opposed by French intelligence and defense ministries.⁽¹⁹⁾⁽²⁰⁾
- An unusual request by the CCP for dozens of biological containment suits for use at the WIV from French manufacturers was denied in 2016, as they were considered an exportation of technologically sensitive equipment.⁽¹⁹⁾
- French intelligence blocked the sale and saw it as evidence the CCP was engaging in bioweapon development.⁽¹⁹⁾
- Following that denial, French researchers were expelled from the WIV in 2017, with cessation of all scientific cooperation, which caused French officials to warn the U.S. State Department of their grave concerns over the true motivations of the CCP towards the WIV.⁽²¹⁾
- In June 2020, the U.S. Department of State (DoS) expressed concerns that China was violating the Biological and Toxin Weapons Convention (BTWC) of 1984 through use of research employing dual-use technologies. The DoS made similar claims in 2005, 2010, 2012 and 2014.⁽⁹⁾
- ***The Epoch Times* story quotes the original 2015 Chinese military study reported in *The Australian* as stating SARS coronaviruses provide the basis for a “new era of genetic weapons” that can be “artificially manipulated into an emerging human**

disease virus, then weaponized and unleashed in a way never seen before.”⁽¹⁰⁾

(Author emphasis)

Epidemiology of SARS-CoV-2 Pointing to the Wuhan Institute of Virology (WIV) as the Viral Source

- The WIV, the Chinese CDC buildings (where BSL-2 level research on coronaviruses is also performed) and the Huanan Wet Market (source of over 40% of early cases of COVID-19) are all situated as stops along the Wuhan Metro Public Railway #2.⁽⁶⁾
- The Wuhan Centers for Disease Prevention and Control (WCDC) is a mere three hundred yards from the Huanan Wet Market. It also studied disease-ridden animals in its research laboratories, which included 605 bats.⁽⁵⁷⁾
- The first group of physicians infected during the initial weeks of the pandemic were at the Wuhan Union Hospital, adjacent to the WCDC.⁽⁵⁷⁾
- The first four Wuhan hospitals to report clinical cases of COVID-19 all straddle the #2 railway, which on a city map of the system runs north to south, carrying one million passengers daily.⁽⁶⁾
- The earliest cases occurred in four individuals interned at the General Hospital of Central Theater Command of the People’s Liberation Army (PLA) of China in Wuhan. These patients had the SARS-CoV-2 genetic types, Clade A and Clade B, the viral lineages which have been the genetic viral variants detected in every patient infected worldwide.

(24)

- The WIV is located less than a mile away from that specific PLA hospital and it's the nearest medical facility to the WIV. In addition, both the WIV and the PLA facility are serviced by Line #2 of the Wuhan Metro railway. ^{(6) (24)}
- To further facilitate the spread of SARS-CoV-2 throughout the city of Wuhan, Line #2 connects with eight other routes, and services the high-speed Hankou Railway Station, enabling facile spread throughout mainland China, as well as the Wuhan (Tianhe) International Airport, enabling quick spread of the virus to Europe, the United States, and the rest of Asia. This is suggested by the dramatically similar genetic strains of SARS-CoV-2 seen in the index patients at the PLA hospital and the international isolates. ^{(6) (24)}
- **The United Nations World Health Organization (WHO) reported on April 23, 2020, that “All the published genetic sequences of SARS-CoV-2 isolated from human cases are very similar. This suggests that the start of the outbreak resulted from a single point introduction in the human population around the time that the virus was first reported in humans in Wuhan, China in December 2019.”** ⁽²³⁾ (Author emphasis)
- **Therefore, the first reported outbreaks of COVID-19 among humans appeared in a city which is home to a virology laboratories that actively perform extensive genetic research on coronaviruses situated on a public transit line that physically connected all of the hospitals and transportation facilities initially involved in the worldwide spread of the virus and is almost two thousand kilometers from the nearest cave serving as habitat to bats infected with potentially genetically comparable viral pathogens.**

- The early SARS-CoV-2 sequences derived from the Huanan Seafood Market are very different from sequences determined from specimens collected at later dates outside of Wuhan. This results in a direct conflict between two primary scientific principles employed in the attempt to infer an outbreak's progenitor, specifically, its genetic sequence should be among the earliest sequences, and that it should be most closely related to deeper ancestors. ⁽⁸⁰⁾

Genetic Clues of SARS-CoV-2 Leading to the Veracity of the Laboratory Leak Theory

- In 2015, the WIV top virologist, Shi Zheng-li, with American virologist, Ralph Baric (Baric is credited with developing a general method for engineering bat coronaviruses to attack other species and admits having taught this technique to Shi) ⁽⁴⁾, published a paper (lead author VD Menachery) ⁽²⁸⁾ describing research creating a chimeric virus by combining the spike protein of a bat coronavirus with a mouse-adapted SARS-CoV-1 backbone.
- The synthetic virus showed robust replication in respiratory cells binding to human angiotensin-converting enzyme II (ACE2), achieving in vitro viral titers equal to epidemic SARS-CoV-1. ⁽²⁸⁾
- **The authors thought this dramatic augmentation in pathogenicity placed this type of research at a crucial crossroads in the execution of so-called “Gain-of-Function” research (GOF).** ⁽²⁸⁾ (Author emphasis)
- This unusual pathogen could have been a prototype to SARS-CoV-2.

- What gave this synthetically produced virus the capacity to infect humans so readily with such high efficiency (infectivity) was the presence of the *Furin Sequence*, a very special, artificially inserted/added cleavage site on the key molecule for cellular entry, the SARS Spike Protein.
- For SARS-CoV-2 to enter a human cell, the virus' primary attachment molecule, the Spike Protein (SP), must first bind to a cellular surface structure called the Angiotensin Converting Enzyme-2 receptor (ACE-2).⁽¹⁾
- After the SP binds to the ACE-2 receptor, a human cell-surface enzyme, the TMPRSS2 is activated, cleaving the SP at a very specific location within the viral attachment structure called the *Furin Cleavage Site (FCS)*, a series of arginine molecules (amino acids strung along the protein chain). Once the TMPRSS2 binds to these arginine residues and “cuts” the inactive SP, the two subunits, S1 and S2, do their “dirty work,” permitting SARS-CoV-2 access to the interior of the targeted human cell.⁽¹⁾
- FCS have been found in viruses that can infect human cells, such as influenza and HIV.⁽⁶⁾
- **SARS-CoV-2 is a member of the Beta Coronavirus Family. No naturally occurring virus in this entire group has an FCS as part of the native SP structure.**⁽⁶⁾ (Author emphasis)
- Review of a database containing the complete genomic sequences of 386 coronaviruses revealed the complete absence of an FCS.⁽³³⁾
- The first paper using Furin Inhibitors (FI) demonstrating the vital importance for the presence of an FCS for successful coronavirus-cell fusion was published in 2004.⁽³⁴⁾

- **The discovery of a twelve-nucleotide long section in SARS-CoV-2 RNA which coded for a SP containing a four amino acid long segment with arginine residues (FCS), essential for human infectivity and transmission, should have prompted worldwide scientific interest in an artificial source for the pathogen.** (Author emphasis)
- A paper published in *Nature*, “The Proximal Origin of SARS-CoV-2”⁽⁹¹⁾ (March 17, 2020) is remarkable for two very important findings that should have immediately raised serious consideration of a lab synthesis for SARS-CoV-2.
- **First, that the virus was optimized for binding to the human cell receptor, ACE-2.**
- **Second, they reported the presence of the functional polybasic (furin) cleavage site located at the S1-S2 boundary. This second finding should have raised red flags as the furin site does not exist in any naturally occurring beta-coronavirus ever isolated and identified by researchers.** (Author emphasis)
- Interestingly, one of the scientists who authored the “Proximal Origins” article has since recanted his position against a natural source for SARS-CoV-2.⁽⁹⁰⁾⁽⁹³⁾
- A second scientific paper originally published on Feb 19, 2020, titled “Structure, Function and Antigenicity of the SARS-CoV-2 Spike Glycoprotein” appearing in the journal *Cell*⁽⁹⁴⁾ stated the following: **“We found that the SARS-CoV-2 S glycoprotein harbors a furin cleavage site at the boundary between the S₁/S₂ subunits, which is processed during biogenesis and sets this virus apart from SARS-CoV and other SARS-related CoVs.”**⁽⁹⁴⁾ (Author emphasis)
- Additional work published in a paper by Dr. Rossana Segreto from the Department of Microbiology, University of Innsbruck, Austria,⁽⁹⁵⁾ highlights multiple characteristics

possessed by SARS-CoV-2 that make it nearly impossible for the virus to have come from an animal source and most likely, was created in a laboratory.

- Among the most important facts outlined in the paper ⁽⁹⁵⁾ include:
 - When Dr. Shi of the WIV revealed the sequencing work they had performed on SARS-CoV-2 for the first time in January 2020, she showed hundreds of gene sequences of this completely novel virus **but stopped short of showing the furin cleavage site.** (Author emphasis)
 - **The existence of a fat ganglioside-binding domain in the structure of the Spike Protein disagrees with the usual host evasion survival mechanisms seen in other human coronaviruses.** (Author emphasis)
 - The evidence of an unusually high human and mouse peptide mimicry in the Spike Protein structure.
 - The proposal that pangolins are the intermediate host for SARS-CoV-2 is unlikely. Although two pangolin coronaviruses discovered ⁽⁹⁶⁾ exhibited potent binding to human ACE-2, the same SP bound ten times weaker to pangolin ACE-2 and binding to a bat ACE-2 (*Rhinolophus ferreus*) was extremely weak, with almost identical binding affinities for SARS-CoV-2. This suggests that neither of the pangolin coronaviruses had developed a solid adaptation to pangolins, and that the ability of coronaviruses to spread among pangolins will require more investigation.
 - In contrast to other species shown to be able to be infected successfully by coronaviruses, pangolins are not trafficked together live and caged together for

any extended period to permit an exchange of viruses leading to viral enhancement and recombination.

- Pangolins are solitary creatures, critically endangered due to poaching and a lively black market for illegal medicinals, possess limited infection resistance and have been shown in a recent screening of a total of 334 pangolins in the wild that these animals have no evidence of coronavirus infections. ⁽⁹⁷⁾
- There is no existing record showing an early evolutionary adaptation of the SARS-CoV-2 ACE-2 Spike Protein binding domain from any animal to humans, which is exceptionally enhanced to bind to human ACE-2.
- **Bats have been shown to be natural reservoirs of SARS-like viruses, so the binding of SARS-CoV-2 would predictably be extremely high to their native ACE-2 proteins. Instead, bat species exposed to SARS-CoV-2 are very poorly infected by the virus, making it extremely unlikely for them to be the source of COVID-19.** (Author emphasis)
- In comparison, the association of poor bat susceptibility and an extremely high human adaptation seen in the earliest strains of SARS-CoV-2 contrasts greatly with the viral evolution seen during the MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-1 outbreaks. **SARS-CoV-2 was remarkably good “fit” for infection in humans while poorly suited to infect bats.** (Author emphasis)
- **Not only is SARS-CoV-2 the only Beta-Coronavirus (Sarbecovirus) to contain a furin cleavage site, ⁽⁹⁸⁾ no naturally occurring coronavirus with a Spike Protein similarity of more than 40% to SARS-CoV-2 possesses a furin cleavage site.** (Author emphasis)

- The insertion of furin cleavage sites has been an extremely common technique employed in GoF research and can be easily introduced using seamless technology ⁽⁹⁹⁾ ⁽¹⁰⁰⁾ without requiring successive cell passage. The probability of a natural mutation resulting in a segment of twelve amino acids coding for a human-optimized furin cleavage site without any known natural intermediate species in Sarbecovirus is infinitesimally low; the introduction of an artificially created furin cleavage site is a far more frugal evolutionary means of achieving a SARS-CoV-2 highly adapted to human infection without a bat-intermediate host.
- **Finally, it is curious that SARS-CoV-2 possesses a fifteen-fold stronger binding affinity for human ACE-2 when compared to SARS-CoV-1.** ⁽¹⁰¹⁾
(Author emphasis)
- **By 2017, the WIV had openly revealed through the publication of multiple scientific papers, that it had developed the necessary laboratory techniques to collect novel coronaviruses, to modify and improve the virus' receptor binding domain permitting human transmission, to insert furin sites allowing human cell infection, to create both chimera and synthetic viruses, the ability to perform experiments in humanized mice, and to modify a gene called ORF8, thus increasing the lethality of the artificial virus to promote human cell death (apoptosis).** ⁽⁶⁾ ⁽³⁵⁾ (Author emphasis)
- **Therefore, the WIV had all the scientific technology necessary to create a virus like SARS-CoV-2.** (Author emphasis)
- These types of experiments are commonly known as *Gain of Function (GoF)*.

Gain of Function (GoF) As It Pertains to SARS-CoV-2

- “GoF involves experimentation that aims or is expected to increase the transmissibility and/or virulence of pathogens.”⁽³⁶⁾
- Another way to describe GoF research would be any investigation designed to introduce *de novo* genetic mutations conferring altered functionality to a specified protein or other essential pathogenic cellular molecule.⁽³⁷⁾
- Despite potential benefits, these types of investigations can be engaged for both benevolent or malevolent purposes, which is why in 2014 the Obama Administration ordered a “temporary pause” on federal funding of GoF involving influenza, SARS, and MERS viruses.⁽³⁶⁾
- Scientists who promote this type of research say such artificial modifications both improve the understanding of disease pathogenesis and spur progress towards medical countermeasures to combat yet to emerge infectious diseases.⁽³⁷⁾
- Before the emergence of SARS-CoV-2, GoF research had provoked controversy, particularly as related to *Dual Use Research of Concern* (DURC).⁽³⁷⁾
- DURC, a subset of microbiology investigations can, as defined by the US government, “be reasonably anticipated to provide knowledge, information, products, or technologies that could be directly misapplied to pose a significant threat with broad potential consequences to public health and safety, agricultural crops and other plants, animals, the environment, materiel, or national security.”⁽³⁸⁾

- Some possible consequences of DURC include the manipulation of pathogens for use as biological weapons with modifications permitting the newly created organisms to evade countermeasures. ⁽³⁹⁾
- These possibilities have raised concerns among funders for biological research, such as the National Institutes of Health (NIH), that such research **“could be used for intentionally harmful purposes or result in an accidental release of pathogens from the laboratory into the general population.”** ⁽³⁷⁾ (Author emphasis)
- Some critical of DURC and GoF argue that these kinds of experiments should be exclusively conducted in strictly monitored BSL-4 labs, thus decreasing the possibility of accidental release and creation of a potentially devastating pandemic. ⁽⁴⁵⁾
- The debate over DURC/GoF will continue, as the unfortunate truth is that many countries, including the United States, are routinely conducting, and funding this type of research, whether for purely scientific purposes, or for malevolent intent. The reality is that there will be future pandemics as opening this biological “Pandora’s Box” remains too tempting to resist. ⁽⁵⁶⁾

Conclusions

A careful read of this essay should lead the reader to a series of specific conclusions:

- SARS-CoV-2 originated in Wuhan, China.
- Based on the epidemiological evidence presented in great detail in earlier sections, the WIV was clearly the epicenter source of the virus.

- The Wuhan Institute of Virology has been conducting delicate, repeated genetic manipulations of coronavirus for many years, as shown in multiple publications originating from the institute.
- The appearance of an unnatural beta-coronavirus, highly adapted for efficient infection of human beings, essentially unable to infect bats, not found to be harbored by any other animal source, appeared in a city home to one of the only coronavirus experimenting labs in the entire world.
- The presence of a furin cleavage site, commonly inserted artificially in a lab as part of Gain of Function research, exists unnaturally in SARS-CoV-2.
- Human viruses, such as HIV and influenza, possess furin cleavage sites which is what allows them to infect human cells. No beta-coronavirus in nature has that capability.
- The CCP has systematically obstructed all serious attempts to uncover the source of the virus, denying any international bodies outside of a small group of WHO officials free access to the WIV, its databases, or researchers. ⁽¹⁴²⁾ ⁽¹⁴³⁾
- The PRC military have openly espoused their plans to weaponize biological agents, specifically mentioning the use of coronaviruses in their official publications.
- The United States, via the NIH, NIAID and private and public universities, have either funded or provided vital biotechnology advancing the CCP's ability to create bioweapons through the sponsoring of Gain of Function research.
- For whatever reasons, the United States politicians, the Mainstream Media, and Tech Giants systematically silenced any voices promoting the possibility of an accidental laboratory leak as the source of COVID-19, despite copious scientific evidence published

early on in 2020 detailing genetic findings pointing to an unnatural source for SARS-CoV-2, and the lack of any documented animal source.

- This writer supports an international ban on all future Gain of Function research as this “Pandora’s Box,” once opened, could lead to a far deadlier pandemic than the current COVID-19 outbreak. The present-day mortality of omicron variant COVID-19 is approaching that of a serious case of influenza (1-2%), particularly for the elderly and immunocompromised, but a future pandemic with a virus capable of >10-15% mortality could ultimately cripple human civilization and bring about its collapse into chaos and anarchy with the disintegration of national governments. Unfortunately, due to GoF’s utility in the development of future bioweapons, this kind of research will likely never stop, placing Mankind’s survival at ever greater risk.

The unfortunate truth is that although this essay presents a mountain of direct scientific and circumstantial evidence pointing to an accidental laboratory release of SARS-CoV-2, until there is a change of regime in Beijing, with replacement of the CCP, we may never be able to conclusively “prove” the lab leak theory, especially as all early samples of the virus were destroyed by the CCP.

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Other Publications by S.E.S. Medina, MD

Please find below the links to all my currently published pieces:

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A colorful, allegorical account of how HIV infects our body (765 words).

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A 1457-word treatise on the real facts surrounding the Philosophers’ Stone. (Short version)

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8) *Doc in a Box* pg 76

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Author bio pg 91

9) *The Philosophers' Stone: History, Myth, Chemistry and Modern Medical Applications*
(extended length version) (4753 words)

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